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UNMASKING CHILD SEX TRAFFICKING: EDUCATION, IDENTIFICATION, AND
SCREENING FOR CALIFORNIA SCHOOL NURSES

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By

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ABSTRACT

California has the highest rate of human trafficking (HT) in the United States (Human Rights Center, 2024). HT includes Child Sex Trafficking (CST) and the Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children (CSEC), in which victims are typically between 11-14 years old and attend school. School nurses (SN) are morally and legally bound to intervene but often lack HT knowledge and resources, such as a screening tool. Guided by the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM), this descriptive mixed methods project surveyed active SNs from the California School Nurses Organization (CSNO). SN participants' awareness of CSEC/CST was measured through pre-and post-surveys. A HT educational module was created, informed by the literature and gaps in knowledge identified by pre-survey results. The post-survey requested feedback on a recommended CST screening tool. Significant findings were an increase in almost all Likert scale categories. Notably, participants indicated increased awareness of sex trafficking (100%) and knowledge of CSEC terminology (83%). They indicated more confidence in their ability to identify at-risk students (151%), coercion methods (146%), as well as high-risk situations & red flags (99%). Lastly, 92% of post-survey participants agreed that the recommended screening tool was appropriate, thus paving the way for future work on a screening tool tailored to SNs. The findings highlight the effectiveness of educational interventions but also emphasize the need for sustained education and a screening tool to address the hidden nature of HT.

Keywords: School Nurse, human trafficking, child sex trafficking, commercial exploitation of children, child sexual abuse, Socio-Ecological Model, California School Nurses Organization, screening tool, and school nurse education.

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Background

Human trafficking (HT) is a lucrative industry and a hidden and complex crime, with perpetrators operating under the radar with low risk and victims often not self-identifying as such (Office for Victims of Crime Training and Technical Assistance Center [OVCTTAC], 2024). It is estimated to generate \$150 billion in annual revenue globally (Office of the Attorney General, 2024). There are two forms of HT, which are sex and labor (Office on Trafficking in Persons [OTIP], 2020). According to the United States (U.S.) Department of State (2020), the fall of the former Soviet Union in the 1990s, the influx of migration, and the flourishing of international criminal organizations brought HT to the world stage. U.S. Department of State (2020), through the Department's Annual Country Reports on Human Rights, began to surveil the sex trafficking (ST) of women and girls. In 2000, the 106th Congress passed The Trafficking Victims Protection Act (TVPA), the first federal law to protect sex and labor trafficking victims, prosecute traffickers, and prevent HT globally (U.S. Department of State, 2020). Under the TVPA, the Secretary of State must submit a report to Congress annually that places countries in a ranking system based on individual government HT prevention efforts (U.S. Department of State, 2020).

Obtaining reliable data is difficult due to the illegal nature of HT (U.S. Department of State, 2020). However, in 2021, the National Center for Missing & Exploited Children (NCMEC) received over 17,200 child sex trafficking (CST) reports from all 50 states, Washington D.C., Puerto Rico, and rural, urban, tribal, and suburban settings (NCMEC, n.d.). In 2019, The National Human Trafficking Hotline reported that 5,359 out of 22,326 identified trafficking victims and survivors were under 18 (U.S. Department of Education, n.d.).

HT or trafficking in persons (TIP) involves the “compelling or coercing a person to provide labor or services, or to engage in commercial sex acts” (United States Department of

Justice [USDOJ], 2023). The broad definition of HT does not require the movement of travel, nor does it apply to children under 18 (Greenbaum et al., 2018a). Traffickers may coerce their victims through physical or psychological means, which can be overt or subtle (USDOJ, 2023).

Child Sex Trafficking/Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children

Child sex trafficking (CST), which falls under commercial sexual exploitation of children (CSEC), is a form of transactional child sexual abuse (CSA) (Barnert et al., 2017; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017). CST is defined as “the recruitment, harboring, transportation, provision, obtaining, patronizing, or soliciting of a minor for the purpose of a commercial sex act” (USDOJ, 2023, para. 1). CST is a type of HT and is an “emerging public health threat” (Doiron & Peck, 2022, p. 5). Several kinds of CST exist, including pimp-controlled, gang-controlled, familial, and buyer-perpetrated trafficking (National Center for Missing & Exploited Children [NCMEC], n.d.). On the other hand, CSEC consists of any sexual crime committed against a juvenile for financial gains, such as prostitution, sex tourism, and trafficking for sexual purposes (Greenbaum et al., 2018). According to California’s Office of the Attorney General (2017), the typical age range for victims of CST in the U.S. is between 11 and 14.

CSEC/CST Entry

Misconceptions about CSEC/CST entry points frequently lead people to believe that victims are foreign nationals or kidnapped children (McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Murdock et al., 2022). However, the grooming and recruitment of a child by their own family members, peers, and close friends is a known HT entry point (Cole, 2018; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Murdock et al., 2022). Furthermore, exploiters use platforms like social media applications, gaming networks, and the Internet to groom their

victims (Fraley et al., 2020). Thus, any child, regardless of gender, race, class, or ethnicity, can be a target of HT (OTIP, 2020).

Several situations place children at an increased risk, such as unstable housing, a history of domestic violence and sexual abuse, a caregiver or family member with substance misuse, family associations to trafficking, youth who have run away or in the foster care system, school failure, and drug and alcohol addiction (Barnert et al., 2017; Cole, 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017, McMahon-Howard & Reimers., 2013; Murdock et al., 2022). Unaccompanied minors without legal immigration status, lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer/questioning (LGBTQ) youth, and those with disabilities are also at an increased risk (U.S. Department of State, 2020).

The novel coronavirus (COVID) pandemic has globally exacerbated the risk of exploitation of children. The NCMEC reported that online exploitation increased from one million in April 2019 to three million in April 2020 (Doiron & Peck, 2022). COVID has left many families struggling financially, creating an even more vulnerable situation for children at risk of trafficking (Doiron & Peck, 2022).

Implications for California

California has one of the highest volumes of HT activity in the U.S., with Los Angeles County serving as one of two main hubs, the other being Alameda County (Human Rights Center, 2024). Since 2007, The Human Trafficking Hotline in California has received 44,942 signals, of which 12,696 resulted in identified cases with over 24,000 victims identified (National Human Trafficking Hotline, n.d.). California passed Assembly Bill (AB) 1227, The Human Trafficking Prevention Education and Training Act, in October 2017 (Office of the Attorney General, 2017). AB 1227 requires public schools to provide HT identification and

prevention through education and training for educators and 7-12th grade students (Office of the Attorney General, 2017). According to the California Department of Education's [CDE] website, 1,021 school districts served 5,892,240 public and charter school students at 10,558 schools during the 2021-2022 school year (CDE, 2022).

California School Nurses

According to the National Association of School Nurses [NASN] (2021), schools are one setting where traffickers recruit children. During the 2018-2019 school year, 2,720 SNs worked in California's K-12 public educational system (CDE, n.d.). A SN is often the only trusted healthcare provider (HCP) in the school setting with frequent access to and interactions with students; thus, it is at the crux of identifying at-risk youth and CSEC/CST victims (Fraley et al., 2018). The California School Nurses Organization (CSNO), the state chapter of the NASN, adopted a HT position in 2017. It noted that credentialed SNs play a vital role in the identification, education, and case management of students who may be at risk for trafficking (CSNO, 2022). However, SNs lack access to formal training about the trafficking of youth, specifically CSEC/CST, and lack empirical tools for screening all forms of child abuse (CA) since there is no formal program or empirical tool to guide their practice.

Health Implications for CSEC/CST Victims

CSEC/CST victims can suffer from adverse physical and mental health effects due to physical violence, sleep deprivation, lack of adequate nutrition, and sexual trauma (McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Murdock et al., 2022; Rapoza, 2022). Some of the adverse health effects include eating disorders, unplanned pregnancy, sexually transmitted infections, exposure to Human Papilloma Virus, Hepatitis B, C, and D, Human Immunodeficiency Virus, untreated chronic diseases, injuries sustained from violence, major depression, suicidality, substance

misuse complications, and other mental health problems (Barnert et al., 2017; Doiron & Peck, 2022; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2017; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Grace et al., 2012; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rapoza, 2022). However, many times, traffickers will allow their victims to seek medical care since, without it, the victim's street value may suffer (Rapoza, 2022).

In many healthcare settings, victims present to a facility while still under their trafficker's control, and providers are often unaware of red flags and thus do not intervene (Ellis et al., 2022; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2017; Rapoza, 2022). Several studies have reported that many CSEC/CST victims attend school; therefore, SNs are more likely to encounter them (Fraley et al., 2018; Grace et al., 2012). This situation provides an opportune time for SNs, well-positioned to identify at-risk youth, to identify red flags and intervene, given that their trafficker is not physically present (Fraley et al., 2018; Sekhar et al., 2018).

Problem Statement

Both the NASN and CSNO have adopted HT position statements that outline the importance of HT awareness for SNs so that they can provide education, early identification, and intervention (CSNO, 2022; NASN, 2021). However, neither organization has recommended a standardized HT tool that SNs can utilize. A standardized instrument and protocol are warranted, given that 87% of identified HT victims reported seeing a healthcare professional during their trafficking experience and were not recognized as victims (Peck & Doiron, 2022). Although HT awareness is increasing, limited training is geared toward nurses in all specialty areas (Peck & Doiron, 2022).

For SNs, a lack of appropriate HT education and knowledge results in ineffective responses in the school environment (Doiron & Peck, 2022). If SNs have the necessary training and a practical screening tool, they can significantly improve the lives of children at risk for HT.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to develop an evidence-based HT educational model, inclusive of CST, tailored to California (CA) SNs and sought their input on a validated CST screening tool for use in their practice settings. The specific objectives were to a) assess the level of HT awareness among CA SNs; b) create an educational module addressing any knowledge gaps; c) collaborate with the CSNO State Board to distribute pre-surveys to all CSNO members on their listserv; d) distribute the educational module to all CSNO members who indicated an interest in the initial survey; e) elicit feedback on a validated evidence-based CST screening tool; and f) distribute post-surveys to assess the module's effect on participant's level of awareness of and attitudes about CSEC/CST.

Supporting Framework: The Socio-Ecological Model

The Socio-Ecological Model

The socio-ecological model (SEM) is a conceptual framework introduced in the 1970s by Urie Bronfenbrenner, a Russian American psychologist (Kilanowski, 2017). His theory, originally known as the ecological systems theory, was a conceptual model that sought to understand human development and is illustrated by overlapping rings that represented the various factors that affect an individual's health (Kilanowski, 2017). Specifically, SEM examines the interaction between individual, community, and environmental characteristics and political, social, and physical factors (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Kilanowski, 2017; Peck, 2020).

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) adapted the SEM to address topics around health promotion, including violence prevention. To understand the factors contributing to violence and to examine prevention intervention effects, the CDC categorized the SEM model into four levels (CDC, 2022). The four levels outlined are the individual, relationship, community, and societal as shown in Appendix A. The model also includes factors within each level that place an individual at risk of experiencing violence or becoming a perpetrator (CDC, 2022; Peck, 2020).

SEM Definitions

There is a complex interplay between all four SEM levels, represented by the overlapping rings. Furthermore, these rings illustrate how factors within each level can influence factors associated with another level (CDC, 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). To understand each level and the factors at play, examining what constitutes each level closely is essential.

Individual

The individual level refers to personal history and biological factors that increase the chance of becoming a victim of violence or an aggressor (CDC, 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). Factors include a history of abuse, age, education, and the use of substances. Strategies to prevent violence at the individual level include socio-emotional learning, conflict resolution, life skills training, and skill programs for learning about healthy dating and relationships (CDC, 2022).

Relationship

The relationship level looks at an individual's inner circle, specifically close relationships that may place them at a higher risk of experiencing violence or becoming a perpetrator (CDC, 2022). These relationships can be familial, peer, or partner-based and must directly impact the

individual's behavior and lived experience (CDC, 2022; Peck, 2020). Prevention strategies at this level focus on the family, peers, and mentoring; it may also include teaching skills on problem-solving, creating healthy relationships, effective parent-child communication, and encouraging positive peer interaction (CDC, 2022).

Community

The community level includes any environment that plays a pivotal role in an individual's relationship development that may be associated with victimization or perpetration, such as their school and neighborhood (CDC, 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). Prevention strategies target improving the social and physical landscape to create safer communities and address conditions that may cause some to be more susceptible to violence, such as poverty, residential segregation, and a high concentration of liquor stores (CDC, 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). Additional prevention efforts include policy and process changes and increasing awareness among professionals who regularly interact with youth, such as healthcare professionals and teachers (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020).

Societal

This level broadens the lens by examining societal factors' influence on whether a society's climate incites or inhibits violence (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). This broader lens examines social and cultural norms that promote violence to resolve problems and explores factors such as educational, economic, health, and social policies that affect particular groups' social determinants of health (CDC, 2022). Furthermore, capitalism, federal and state legislation and policies regarding child trafficking, and societal and community awareness also fall under this level (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). Strategies geared toward prevention at this level include addressing the structural determinants of health, such as policies for financial security among

households, education, and employment opportunities, and supporting societal norms that promote nonviolence (CDC, 2022; Peck, 2020).

SEM Literature Review

Previous research has applied the SEM in various settings and disciplines to examine various topics and the factors at play. There are several studies in the literature in which researchers applied the SEM as their conceptual model to guide their understanding of violence prevention, including CST and commercial sexual exploitation of children (CSEC).

SEM Use in Child Sex Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children

Finigan-Carr et al. (2019) applied SEM to their research on CST to extend beyond focusing on individual risk factors, often seen in the literature, to include social norms' influence on all four levels of the SEM. This application broadened the analysis of CST to include social, political, and cultural influences. The authors argue that children are embedded into multiple settings throughout their day, allowing them to be influenced at various levels identified in the SEM (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019).

The individual level is influenced by internalized beliefs and behaviors shaped by social norms at the other three SEM levels (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). Findings that place a child at an increased risk for CST include mental health problems, a history of trauma including abuse, substance use and addiction, and homelessness (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). Findings at the relationship level addressed the interpersonal factors that influence the likelihood of CST involvement in the home and among peers. These included family and peer involvement in the sex trade, dysfunctional homes, and the normalization of sex work among the community, peers, and family (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019).

At the community level, factors influencing CST vulnerability include neighborhoods and schools where social relationships develop. Several factors that increase the risk for CST at this level include poverty and discrimination against marginalized youth based on race, class, gender, and sexual orientation (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). At the societal level, factors that add to CST vulnerability include community and societal awareness, federal and state trafficking legislation, and a culture of capitalism, which influence how communities and society conceive CST (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019).

The application of SEM by Finigan-Carr et al. (2019) uncovered the social stigmas that provoke structural influences and inequalities at the root of CST, specifically those faced by marginalized groups due to gender, sexuality, age, race/ethnicity, and poverty. Understanding these deep-rooted factors can lead to developing directed CST prevention and intervention strategies.

SEM in Schools

Butler et al. (2022) applied SEM during their literature review on cannabis use among youth to classify common risk and protective factors directly related to the school environment. Specifically, Butler et al. (2022) categorized articles by themes based on four SEM levels: individual, interpersonal, community, and societal. Using SEM, they identified that school connectedness and climate were protective factors among vulnerable youth, specifically LGBTQ and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds (Butler et al., 2022). Furthermore, their findings point to schools being a setting for both risks, such as bullying and truancy, and protective factors, such as high academic performance and achievement. The authors argue that mixed findings of the influence of some factors may be due to the uniqueness of each school's environment or student population; thus, schools should be cognizant of risk and protective

factors specific to their student population (Butler et al., 2022). Individual and school-level factors were seen to have the highest influence on risk and protective factors. Notably, a positive school climate had an inverse relationship with cannabis use (Butler et al., 2022).

SEM Use with School Nurses

There is limited available research on using SEM with SNs as it applies to CSEC/CST. However, several studies have used the SEM to look at violence prevention in schools, including bullying, and one study involved SNs.

Reisner et al. (2020) applied SEM to identify individual, interpersonal, and structural factors that facilitate or hamper school health professionals (SHPS), the majority being school nurses (SNs), in reporting and responding to bullying of LGBTQ students. This study addressed these factors through the lens of 19 SHPs and 28 LGBTQ students in Massachusetts. LGBTQ youth face higher rates of victimization, psychological distress, physical injury, and suicide; they are often likely to encounter SNs when they present to the health office with mental and physical complaints (Reisner et al., 2020). There are limited evidence-based interventions to support SHPs in preventing, identifying, and addressing bullying among this population, and there is a need for staff training related to LGBTQ issues (Reisner et al., 2020). The authors argued that addressing bullying requires addressing the following: 1) societal stigmatization (e.g., racism, sexism, homophobia, transphobia); 2) organizational culture (e.g., healthcare, schools); 3) interpersonal system (e.g., families, peers, teachers); and 4) individual factors (e.g., personal attitudes and knowledge) (Reisner et al., 2020).

The study's findings showed that SHPs needed to increase their knowledge, acceptance, skills, and handling of LGBTQ-related topics, which student participants shared. Furthermore, both groups agreed that having resources available to SHPs would facilitate more competent and

timely responses to bullying (Reisner et al., 2020). Individual factors shared by both groups addressed the fact that resistant personal beliefs and attitudes of SHPs were barriers. LGBTQ participants also stated that SHPs need training on empathy and should be aware of the importance of intersectionality among LGBTQ youth's identities and the issues unique to LGBTQ students of color (Reisner et al., 2020).

One interpersonal barrier shared by LGBTQ participants was a lack of trust in SHPs when they did not follow through with reporting after the student placed their trust in them to do so. The student participants also voiced that establishing a close relationship with SHPs helped to lessen their fears of being "outed." Student and SHP participants stressed the need for buy-in from key stakeholders and promoting inclusive school culture at the administration level to help mitigate bullying (Reisner et al., 2020). Organizational and structural level barriers identified by SHPs and LGBTQ participants were a lack of clarity regarding SHPs' roles and responsibilities, limited staffing, and time, which resulted in preventing SHPs from helping, especially when it came to follow-up (Reisner et al., 2020). Identified facilitators by SHPs to prevent bullying included having protocols, guidance, and clear reporting guidelines (Reisner et al., 2020). SEM provided a foundation to uncover multilevel factors that impact an SHP's ability to report and respond to LGBTQ bullying through the perspectives of LGBTQ youth and SHPs; these identified factors can then inform the creation of tailored interventions (Reisner et al., 2020).

Application of SEM with California School Nurses' Addressing CSEC/CST

Within the context of CSEC/CST, the SEM is an appropriate multi-level framework that guided the selection of an evidence-based tool and development of an education module for California SNs. The SEM provides a holistic perspective for understanding CSEC/CST as it relates to a child's individual, relational, community, and societal environment (CDC, 2022;

Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). The project intervention focused on the community level since the school setting is where SNs will likely encounter students at risk of being exploited (Fraley et al., 2018; Grace et al., 2012). Although this project's focus was at the community level, the screening tool and educational module addressed multiple levels of the SEM due to the dynamic relationships and factors across all levels.

Individual

The adapted socio-ecological model placed the student at its center as shown in Appendix B. Although any child can be a target of CST/CSC, several descriptors place a child at increased risk, including 1) children between the ages of 11-14, 2) unstable housing, 3) a history of domestic violence and sexual abuse, 4) a caregiver or family member with substance misuse, 5) missing from care or in the foster care system, 6) drug and alcohol addiction, 7) LGBTQ, and 8) having disabilities (Barnert et al., 2017; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2017; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022; Richie-Zavaleta et al., 2020). The tool and educational module highlighted these high-risk factors that SNs should be cognizant of.

Relationship

The relationship level of the tool and educational module looked explicitly at factors that involved the family and peer context. These factors included dysfunctional and unstable home environments such as domestic violence, substance misuse, poverty, unsafe housing, and child maltreatment that places a child at an increased risk of CSEC/CST (Austin et al., 2020; Cole, 2018; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). In addition, family and peer involvement in the sex trade and the normalization of sex work among the community, peers, and family were also included (Cole, 2018; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019).

Community

Children are influenced and embedded in different landscapes as they move throughout various communities within their day, including their neighborhood and school. The community level, particularly the school environment, can profoundly impact a child's development, including the influence of victimization (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). Research has shown that truancy, low academic performance, and being a victim of bullying are known risk factors for CSEC/CST among school youth (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2017). The school community, specifically SNs, was the target intervention for this project. Nursing is considered the most trusted profession, and nurses are trained in therapeutic communication and interacting with vulnerable patients (Peck, 2020). SNs are well positioned to identify children at risk of CSEC/CST given their daily interactions within the school setting; however, they often lack sufficient knowledge and awareness of CSEC/CST (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Grace et al., 2012). This level profoundly impacted the other levels of SEM since it equipped SNs with the knowledge and skills to identify, intervene, and prevent CSEC/CST and a tangible evidence-based screening tool.

Societal

Decisions made at the societal level will directly impact the community as governmental processes and policies dictate what resources will be allocated and what priorities will be made. This level also shapes community awareness and knowledge of CSEC/CST (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). The educational module addressed CST at the societal level, including trafficking policies and legislation at the state and federal levels and position statements by NASN and CSNO. At the state level, California passed AB 1227, The Human Trafficking Prevention Education and Training Act, in October 2017 to bring awareness of HT to educators and 7th-12th grade students

across the state's public schools (Office of the Attorney General, 2017). Federally, TVPA serves to protect trafficking victims, prosecute traffickers, and prevent HT globally (U.S. Department of State, 2020). NASN and CSNO have position statements on HT, but neither has recommended a standardized screening tool for CSEC/CST identification tailored to SNs.

Limitations

Although there is limited published research on the application of SEM with SNs as it relates to CSEC/CST, there are research findings from other disciplines and studies involving SNs that applied SEM and whose methodology and conclusions can be applied to this doctoral project. The SEM served as the project's guide to examine the various layers and factors that place children at risk of being exploited for CSEC/CST. This led to the development of a tailored evidence based CSEC/CST education module and the identification and recommendation of a validated CST screening tool for SNs.

Review of Literature

Methods

This systematic review of the literature identified relevant research on CA and CSEC/CST presentation, available screening tools, and HCPs and SNs' role in identification, education, and prevention. Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health (CINAHL), Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), and Public/Publisher Medline (PubMed) were used during the initial literature search. The initial search terms were “human trafficking,” “child sex trafficking,” “child sex trafficking screening tool,” “child sexual abuse screening tool,” “child sex trafficking education for healthcare providers,” “child sex trafficking education for school nurses,” and the “school nurse's role in child sex trafficking.” In addition, the following limiters were applied: peer-reviewed research articles published between 2017 and 2022, written in English, individuals (0-22 years), and took place in healthcare, community, and school settings. Research studies on adult and labor trafficking were also excluded because they were outside the project's scope, along with integrative reviews, meta-analyses, and topic-interest papers.

APA PsycInfo was added to the list of databases referenced during further searches due to the limited available peer-reviewed research studies (Appendix C). Limiters were expanded to include studies published between 2000 and 2023, as shown in Appendix D, to capture relevant studies. A thorough review of the reference lists from the retrieved literature led to the discovery and inclusion of five additional peer-reviewed research publications.

The review of the literature search followed a systematic approach to identify 22 research studies that were selected based on their relevance to the project, as shown in Appendix D. Of the 22 studies, six were qualitative (Chappell et al., 2021; Fraley et al., 2021b; Hartinger-

Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022; Sekhar et al., 2018), six quantitative (Day et al., 2023; Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hurst et al., 2021; Rheingold et al., 2012), five mixed methods (Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley et al., 2018; Jordan et al., 2017; McMahon-Howard & Reiners, 2013), one systematic review (Chen et al., 2022) and three were quasi-experimental designs (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; Raible et al., 2017).

The studies were grouped into three categories: a) presentation of CA and CSEC/CST in healthcare and school settings, 2) CA & CSEC/CST screening tools and 3) CA and CSEC/CST education. For SNs, the lack of appropriate CSEC/CST education and knowledge leads to ineffective and uncoordinated responses in the school setting (Doiron & Peck, 2022). If SNs are equipped with the necessary information, skills, and a practical screening tool, they can significantly improve the lives of children at risk of CSEC/CA. This review informed the development of a tailored evidence-based CSEC/CST education module and the selection of a validated screening tool, including CA, for California SNs to use within their practice setting.

Due to the limited available research on CA and CSEC/CST, most studies selected were qualitative and employed focus groups to gain an understanding of participants' perspectives and experiences. Two studies conducted focus groups with HT survivors to gain insight into their experiences, including encounters with healthcare while being trafficked, and to identify risk factors (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Murdock et al., 2022). Two other studies also used focus groups to understand the perspectives of healthcare and educational professionals and community members in identifying CSA (Chappell et al., 2021; Sekhar et al., 2018). Five studies implemented focus groups with SNs to gain insight into their awareness, knowledge, encounters,

and role perceptions with CA and CSEC/CST (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b; Fraley et al., 2018; Jordan et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018).

CA and CSEC/CST Presentation

This section reviews the literature on CA and CSEC/CST presentations in healthcare and school settings. CA and CSEC/CST presentations can differ between settings and individuals based on clinical presentation and willingness to disclose (Chappell et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2022; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Sekhar et al., 2018). Furthermore, many victims of trafficking do not recognize themselves as such, which makes identification difficult (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; McMahan-Howard & Reimers, 2013).

In school health offices, survivors noted that they felt invisible to their SNs who did not recognize red flags, particularly repeated visits due to physical complaints such as stomach pain, nausea, menstrual cramping, and migraines (Fraley et al., 2018; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Kraft et al., 2017). On the other hand, in healthcare settings such as the emergency department (ED), victims often present with overt trauma, such as sustained injuries needing emergent care (Chen et al., 2022; Murdock et al., 2022). In multiple studies, HCPs and SNs reported overlooking or mistaking presenting health symptoms, such as anxiety, suicidal tendencies, stomach pain, self-injurious behavior, and eating disorders; often, they did not attribute these symptoms to CA (Ellis et al., 2022; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Kraft et al., 2017).

HCPs, SNs, and HT survivor participants also discussed the presentation of genitourinary infections across multiple healthcare settings (Chappell et al., 2021; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Hurst et al., 2021); however, in the school setting, cramping was often attributed to one's menstrual cycle rather than secondary to urinary infection (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a).

Participant perspectives unique to schools and shared by SNs and HT survivors included frequent visits to the health office due to hunger, falling asleep, and using metaphors to disclose difficult experiences (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Kraft et al., 2017). For instance, a survivor recalling past school experiences in one study revealed she was forced to sit on an adult male's lap, comparing herself to a remote-controlled car when describing her experience (Kraft et al., 2017).

Several studies also addressed the implicit and explicit bias held by some HCPs and SNs toward youth victims, such as viewing CST as prostitution through a criminal lens and failing to see children as victims but rather as culprits who voluntarily chose these paths and consensually engage in risky behaviors (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley et al., 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022). These shared beliefs led to unequal treatment and created barriers to a victim's ability to engage with a HCP (Murdock et al., 2022). Furthermore, it resulted in the misdiagnosis of children who presented with clear signs of abuse, such as being diagnosed with other physical ailments or having their abuse associated with other types of abuse rather than CST (Kraft et al., 2017).

Limitations

Potential limitations identified by multiple studies about CA and CSEC/CST presentation include survivor experiences are ungeneralizable and are dependent on a myriad of individual, community, and societal factors and norms (Chappell et al., 2021; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Sekhar et al., 2018). These studies demonstrate the highly individualistic nature of CA and CSEC/CST presentations and disclosures, emphasizing the need for HCPs and SNs to pay close attention to various presentations.

Screening for CA and CSEC/CST

This section reviewed the literature on available CA and CSEC/CST screening tools. Although screening tools are available for CA and CSEC/CST, they are often used inconsistently across healthcare settings (Chappell et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2022; Day et al., 2023; Ellis et al., 2022). Multiple studies have found several barriers to screening and reporting, including a lack of suitable screening questions tailored toward adolescents, knowledge, limited training, time constraints, and murky referral procedures (Chappell et al., 2021; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). The disclosure process, including screenings, can be complex, uncertain, and time-consuming without a valid and user-friendly screening tool (Chen et al., 2022; Day et al., 2023; Fraley et al., 2018; Greenbaum et al., 2018b).

CA Screening Tools

CA screening tools have been used in various healthcare settings (Chen et al., 2022; Day et al., 2023). A systematic review designed to critically appraise the methodology of 15 CA screening tools for children <18 revealed the variability of available tools used across healthcare (Chen et al., 2022). Studies in which the tool was used to screen patients who presented to an HCP due to physical, emotional, and sexual abuse and neglect met the requirements for article inclusion. Of the 15 tools appraised by Chen et al. (2022), more than half screened for physical abuse (n=9), while only one screened for sexual abuse; the number of screening tool items also varied from one to 31. The study concluded that although none of the 15 tools screened for all forms of CA, many tools had moderate to high levels of evidence and are helpful in community and healthcare settings (Chen et al., 2022).

In the study by Day et al. (2023), 56 at-risk (confirmed history of abuse) and 195 participants not at-risk, ages 13 and older, completed the Teen Hurt-Insult-Threaten-Scream-Sex (TeenHITSS) and Conflict Tactics Scale: Parent-Child Version (CTSPC), both in English and Spanish. The at-risk participants were recruited by domestic violence and abuse shelter staff or an at-risk referral clinic, and the not-at-risk participants were recruited during their primary care visit in an ambulatory setting (Day et al., 2023).

TeenHITSS is an adaptation of the Pediatric HITSS screening tool, validated in pediatric populations and used to screen for sexual and physical abuse (Day et al., 2023). The five-item tool's content asks teens how frequently they encounter the following in their own homes: 1) physical harm, 2) verbal abuse, 3) physically threatening behavior, 4) cursing or screaming and 5) being forced into having sex; the higher the score. A higher score indicates more frequently occurring abusive behavior, ranging from 0 to 20 (Day et al., 2023).

Based on self-reporting by parents and guardians, the Conflict Tactics Scale: Parent-Child Version (CTSPC) is a validated 22-item screening tool to assess child maltreatment from infancy to 17 years of age (Day et al., 2023). The participants answered questions on physical abuse and psychological aggression, and two supplemental questions were added on sexual abuse as part of the child version subscales. Participants were prompted to answer each question by being asked how frequently a member of their immediate family engaged in the relevant subscale behavior. A 7-point Likert scale was used to rate the frequency of abuse, with a score of zero denoting never and a score of six denoting more than 20 times. The sexual abuse items were rated using a 3-point Likert scale (Day et al., 2023).

Day et al. (2023) found that both tools' full-scale scores, irrespective of the sexual abuse items, had strong concurrent validity ($r=.71$, $p<.000$) and good internal reliability within each

group. There were significant differences in TeenHITSS scores between the full sample, at-risk and no-risk groups ($p < .001$). ROC curve analyses revealed that TeenHITSS, compared to CTSPC, had higher sensitivity and specificity for accurately identifying the participant's group (at-risk vs. not at-risk for adolescent abuse); $AUC = .79$ vs. $.73$, respectively (Day et al., 2023). The authors concluded that TeenHITSS is a valid and reliable tool for screening for physical and sexual abuse in adolescents and offers a shorter alternative for HCPs than CTSPC (Day et al., 2023).

CSEC/CST Screening Tools

Greenbaum et al. (2018a) conducted a cross-sectional study to describe CSEC/CST victim characteristics and create a screening tool to identify victims in high-risk adolescent populations. The study occurred in three pediatric EDs and one child protection clinic in Atlanta, and the 6-item screening tool was administered to English-speaking patients aged 12 to 18. There were 108 patient participants, including three males, classified into two groups. Twenty-five were “suspected CSEC/CST” based on the Institute of Medicine and the United Nations CSEC definition, and 83 were classified as “alleged acute sexual assault/sexual abuse” or ASA based on reported complaints and information gathered during their visit.

The 6-item screening tool content included a previous history of drug and alcohol use, running away, law enforcement involvement, physical trauma (e.g., broken bones, significant wound, traumatic loss of consciousness), STI, and having ≥ 5 sexual partners. Greenbaum et al. (2018a) found that a positive answer cutoff score of ≥ 2 had a sensitivity of 92% and a specificity of 73%; a positive response to ≥ 2 questions increased the odds of being a victim of CSEC/CST by twenty-two times ($p < 0.001$).

Both groups had significant differences on 16 variables related to STI, history of experiencing violence, participation in high-risk behaviors, and reproductive history. Furthermore, statistically significant differences in racial and ethnic differences between the two groups were discovered. In the CSEC/CST group, there were more African Americans or “other” (mixed race, Asian) than in the ASA group ($p=.005$). There was a significant difference in historical, demographic, physical, and behavioral characteristics of alleged CSEC/CST female victims aged 12-18 compared to ASA victims; this tool effectively distinguished between the two (Greenbaum et al., 2018a).

Greenbaum et al. (2018b) conducted a cross-sectional observational study to evaluate a CST screening tool used across 16 healthcare settings, including EDs, teen clinics, and child advocacy centers (CAC). The tool was administered to 11-17-year-old English-speaking patients who presented with acute sexual assault/abuse or CST. The 17-item questionnaire contained nine questions about medical care history and CST risk factors. If the patient acknowledged having sex, eight additional questions regarding sexual history, high-risk behaviors, STIs, and sexual orientation were asked.

If a patient answered yes to two or more questions, they were determined to have a positive screen. Of the 810 patients, 90 or 11% were identified as CST victims. Furthermore, this study had 121 male participants, of which 17% were identified as victims (Greenbaum et al., 2018b). The study’s findings point out that for every six to seven patients an HCP screens due to sexual violence complaints in these settings, one would be identified as a CST victim in a CAC, three to four in a teen clinic, and four in an ED; the tool had good sensitivity, which ranged from 83.3% to 84.9% (Greenbaum et al., 2018b).

Hurst et al. (2021) administered Greenbaum et al.'s (2018a) 6-item validated CST screening tool in English and Spanish at a pediatric ED in a large urban children's hospital. The tool was administered to patients when they were alone using an electronic tablet and included content on substance misuse, sexual history, previous law enforcement involvement, running away, physical violence, and the number of sexual partners. The tool consisted of a categorical question for the number of sexual partners and yes or no questions. A positive screen was determined if a patient answered yes to ≥ 2 questions, which was then followed up with four additional questions asked by the HCP regarding CST behaviors. A referral for a clinical social worker consultation was made, and law enforcement was notified. HCPs also were given a separate Likert-scale checklist regarding HT risk factors used in initial psychometric testing and validation conducted by Greenbaum et al. (2018a). Patients who answered yes to <2 questions were determined to have low risk.

Out of 214 patients screened, 26 screened positive, which indicated a prevalence of 12.3% (Hurst et al., 2021). A history of suicide attempts and CA increased the odds of a patient screening positive for HT and were statistically significant with $p=.004$ and $p=.01$, respectively (Hurst et al., 2021). Furthermore, trafficked individuals were more likely to be tested for STIs, substance misuse, and pregnancy than non-trafficked patients. Like other studies, tool sensitivity was favored over specificity, leading to many false positives ($n=87$); however, the trade-off was deemed warranted (Hurst et al., 2021).

CSA & CSEC/CST Screening Tool

A study by Ellis et al. (2022) combined Greenbaum et al.'s (2018a) CSEC/CST screening tool with a universal CA tool; both addressed physical and sexual abuse. Ellis et al. (2022) conducted a retrospective chart review of urgent care and ED patients aged 11-17 who screened

positive on a universal abuse screen in a Midwest pediatric center. The study aimed to measure the proportion of patient records with positive abuse screens who also had ≥ 2 CSEC/CST indicators. The universal screening tool consisted of four questions on physical and sexual abuse and neglect, two directed at the patient's guardian/parent, and the remaining were for the patient. The six-question CSEC/CST Screening Tool highlighted known risk factors, including a history of alcohol and drug use, law enforcement involvement, and running away from home (Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018a).

Ellis et al. (2022) found that 43% of their sample were patients with ≥ 2 CSEC/CST indicators. In addition, several predictors increased the chance of a patient having ≥ 2 CSEC/CST indicators. These predictors included being older, sexually active, having a mental health complaint, and having a history of running away (Ellis et al., 2022).

Development of a CSA Screening Tool

Sekhar et al. (2018) conducted an exploratory, descriptive study to understand how key stakeholders (i.e., SNs, teachers, administrators, counselors, pediatric providers, and parents) responded to developing a formal CSA screening process, including tool content. The researchers conducted focus groups and used an interview guide and circulation of a proposed tool to encourage discussion. Through qualitative content analysis, participant responses identified three themes: 1) the need for early screening and identification, 2) confidentiality, and 3) refinement of the identification process. Participants across focus groups agreed that educating students on appropriate and inappropriate touching at an early age, defining normal behavior, and consistent messaging on finding a trusted adult to disclose is important.

Participants raised concerns regarding implementing the CSA screening tool, citing whether the school district and parents would approve it, the associated training, and the time for

follow-up for positive results. No consensus was reached on who should administer the tool, where it should be administered, how it should be administered, and the timing of it. There was also no unanimity on the needed content for the screening tool; however, participants did note that questions on feeling safe should be asked (Sekhar et al., 2018). Furthermore, some participants believed that the tool should mimic suicide screening questions or identify at-risk students by applying the concept of an individualized education plan assessment to identify students at risk, address their needs, and facilitate intervention (Sekhar et al., 2018).

Participant Recommendations

Participants in several selected studies included in this literature review provided recommendations for screening. A common theme identified by HT survivors, HCPs, and SNs is the need to provide an outlet for youth to disclose (Chappell et al., 2021; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). Examples included providing a safe space, identifying a designated adult, forming a trusting relationship, expressing compassion, humanizing the survivor, and creative activities to promote disclosure, such as coloring (Chappell et al., 2021; Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022; Raible et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). Furthermore, several studies addressed that interviews and screenings took place without the parent/caregiver or accompanying adult present, which led to in-depth conversations (Day et al., 2023; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hurst et al., 2021). Since research has shown that family involvement with trafficking is a factor in recruitment, screening the child alone is crucial (Barnert et al., 2017; Cole, 2018; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; McMahan-Howard & Reimers, 2013).

Participants across several studies also relayed that the type and delivery of questions mattered, specifically direct questions about home life and experiencing violence (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Kraft et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). Other suggestions to facilitate the disclosure of sensitive information among youth included using an electronic tablet for tool administration and providing a health questionnaire before engaging in dialogue, which led to in-depth conversations that elicited disclosure (Hurst et al., 2021; Kraft et al., 2017).

Limitations

Several limitations were identified in the studies reviewed, including variations in study settings and conditions, participant demographics and cultural norms, and the type of abuse screened. Another limitation is that most screening tools were written in English, with only one translated into Spanish (Hurst et al., 2021). Although none of the tools discussed in this review were used in a school setting, which may threaten external validity, they were useful in identifying at-risk and exploited children across various healthcare settings. Furthermore, given that there are no available tools specific to school settings, the findings help inform the development of tools specific to identifying at-risk youth and for use by SNs.

Tool Integration

The CSA and CSEC/CST tools selected for this review of literature were used in a variety of healthcare settings in the United States, including ED, CACs, urgent cares, and clinics with English and Spanish-speaking patients over the age of ten and under 18 (Day et al., 2023; Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hurst et al., 2021). The six-item CSEC/CST validated screening tool (Appendix M) created by Greenbaum et al. (2018a), employed and assessed in four studies included in this review, is the most suitable for this project since it has been used successfully in various healthcare settings. To create their tool, Greenbaum

et al. (2018a) compared a control group of patients who were seen for allegations of sexual assault or abuse to patients who presented to the ED or child protection clinic in Atlanta with CSEC/CST characteristics (Ellis et al., 2022).

Additionally, various study designs, including cross-sectional observational, quasi-experimental, prospective, and retrospective designs, have successfully implemented it. The sample sizes of the studies that used the six-item tool ranged from 108 to 2,168, and most participants were biologically female (Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hurst et al., 2021). However, this tool has also been used with a significant number of male participants (n=121 or 15.3%), of which 17% were identified in the ED setting and 20% in CACs in a Greenbaum et al. (2018b) study. With a cutoff of two positive responses, this tool had an overall sensitivity of 92%, specificity of 73%, negative predictive value of 97%, and positive predictive value of 51% (Greenbaum et al. 2018a).

Additionally, in the initial study by Greenbaum et al. (2018a), the area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC) was .97, indicating a nearly perfect discriminator of CSEC/CST victims. Using this tool, researchers could distinguish between CSEC/CST victims and ASA victims based on behavioral, physical, demographic, and historical factors (Greenbaum et al., 2018a). The tool successfully identified children at risk for CSEC/CST in all four studies across various settings (Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hurst et al., 2021).

Content. Recommended items to be added to Greenbaum et al.'s screening tool should include additional known risk factors for CSEC/CST recognized in the literature. These risk factors include history of emotional, physical, and sexual abuse, involvement in the juvenile justice system, poor academic performance, and foster and LGBTQ youth (Ellis et al., 2022;

Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley et al., 2018; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017). In addition, mental health vulnerabilities are additional known risk factors noted in the literature (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Greenbaum et al., 2018b).

CA and CSEC/CST Awareness

This section reviewed the literature on CA and CSEC/CST, including HCPs' and SNs' awareness, knowledge, and experiences with CSEC/CST. The majority of studies selected for this literature review addressed the varying degrees of CA and CSEC/CST awareness and knowledge among HCPs, SNs, and the public (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b; Fraley et al., 2018; Gardner et al., 2020; Hartinger-Sanders et al., 2017; Jordan et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Lutz, 2018; Murdock et al., 2022; Sekhar et al., 2018). The variety in awareness and knowledge varied depending on several factors, including communities where one worked, held beliefs, and role perceptions (Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley et al., 2018; Jordan et al., 2017).

CSEC/CST Awareness

Cole and Sprang (2015) conducted a mixed methods sequential explanatory design study to explore the awareness, knowledge, and experiences of professionals who work with at-risk youth and victims of ST across non-metropolitan and metropolitan communities in a rural southern state in the United States. The study aimed to understand the differences and similarities between how ST presents itself and how community agencies respond, which was measured through open and closed-ended survey questions conducted over the telephone with 289 participants. Closed-ended questions were in the form of a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 to 4. The study's measures included community type where the participant was employed,

CSEC/Sex Trafficking of Minors (STM) awareness, and experience working with victims of STM.

The authors found that professionals in metropolitan communities perceived HT as pretty or very serious in the state, whereas all communities believed CSEC to be a severe issue in metropolitan areas (Cole & Sprang, 2015). Furthermore, those in metropolitan communities tended to have received previous HT training compared to micropolitan and rural communities ($p < .001$) and were more knowledgeable about HT state and federal laws ($p < .01$).

Although there were similar trafficking situations, vulnerability factors, recruiting tactics, and victim-trafficker relationships across communities, professionals in micropolitan communities had encounters with STM victims (29.8%) compared to participant respondents in rural (43.6%) and metropolitan (54.7%) communities (Cole & Sprang, 2015).

The authors argue that STM awareness was low among non-metropolitan communities, which warrants attention (Cole & Sprang, 2015). Communities also played a significant role in a study by Fraley et al. (2018). This study found that SNs working in high-risk communities with a diverse student population were more likely to have positive attitudes toward at-risk students (Fraley et al., 2018). Furthermore, CPS participants who worked in rural communities expressed the need for more education specific to rural settings in the study by McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013).

CSEC/CST awareness was also measured psychometrically in a study by Fraley and Aronowitz (2021b). The authors conducted a mixed methods sequential explanatory design to develop and test the psychometric properties of the School Nurses' Awareness and Perceptions Survey (SNAPS) for youth at risk of trafficking, using an iterative multiphase process with SNs in MA and nationally. In Phase 1 of the instrumentation validation study, the authors sought to

understand the SNs' attitudes, role perceptions, and awareness of youth at risk for HT as measured psychometrically through SNAPs. Construct validity was assessed using exploratory factor analysis in Phase 1 and confirmatory factor analysis in Phase 2 (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b).

The researchers administered a revised 44-item instrument during Phase 1 to 96 SNs attending a NASN conference to assess instrument validity. In Phase 2, a revised 5-point Likert scale with a 35-item instrument was administered through an electronic survey to each state chapter NASN membership email listserv, which resulted in 939 school nurses from across the United States (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b). The scale's content was derived in multiple phases through conceptual and theoretical linkages found through literature review and pilot testing with MA SNs. A revised 32-item SNAPs was developed with three sub-scales using a 5-point Likert scale with content on CSEC risk awareness, attitudes, and role perceptions of SNs.

The authors concluded that in both phases, SNAPs had strong psychometric properties and is a valid and reliable tool to measure SNs' attitudes and awareness of students at risk for CSEC. The findings indicate that the revised tool has good internal consistency ($\alpha = .94$) and thus can be used to inform future research and educational interventions (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b).

HCP and Community Education on CA and CSEC/CST

Several studies examined the effect of educational interventions on CA and CSEC/CST awareness among HCPs, CPS employees, nurse practitioner (NP) students, childcare professionals (CCP), and members of the school and church communities (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012).

The studies varied in sampling methodology and settings (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012).

Content. The educational content varied between studies based on the targeted audience and whether the intervention addressed CA or CSEC/CST. In both CA studies (Gardner et al., 2020; Rheingold et al., 2012), the intervention was guided by well-established, reputable educational programs (i.e., train-the-trainer and Stewards of Children). Conversely, the content of CSEC/CST was not based on existing interventions but on general introductory content (Donahue et al., 2019; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). However, all studies systematically reviewed available literature to inform content (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012).

CA. Content for CA included abuser characteristics, the distinction between abuse and discipline, CA and neglect (CAN) indicators, state laws, and how to handle disclosure (Gardner et al., 2020; Rheingold et al., 2012). One study implemented a train-the-trainer program in a community setting and addressed topics on training importance, CAN in the community, child neglect, physical, emotional, and sexual abuse definitions, and examples, and reporting laws and procedures (Gardner et al., 2020).

Stewards of Children, a workshop training run by Darkness to Light (D2L), is a national nonprofit organization whose goal is to prevent CSA through in-person and web-based training for CCPs, served as the foundation for the study by Rheingold et al. (2012). In-person participants received a curriculum workbook that included CSA prevalence, risks, outcomes, risk reduction strategies, CSA recognition, discussion techniques, appropriate disclosure responses, addressing individual and organizational barriers to prevention, and community involvement to reduce CSA (Rheingold et al., 2012). The facilitator also showed a 1.25-hour DVD with

interview segments with the curriculum author, professionals who encountered CSA, and survivors sharing their stories. The interactive web-based content included video clips and was 2.5 hours long (Rheingold et al., 2012).

CSEC/CST. Content for CSEC/CST included defining HT and CSEC/CST, types of CSEC, the domestic and international scope of HT and CSEC, state laws, characteristics of at-risk populations, entrapment stages, red flags, screening questions, pathways to entry, and common health implications (Donahue et al., 2019; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). In the study by McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013), behaviors of CSEC victims, such as not identifying themselves as victims to protect their trafficker, and services available to help CSEC victims, including forensic interviews and medical exams, were also addressed. In addition, recommendations for treatment and identification were included in an evidence-based online training program (HTEmergency.com) in the study by Donahue et al. (2019).

One study assessed student NPs' knowledge of HT across six domains: prevalence, definitions, identification, treatment, and referral process (Lutz, 2018). However, specific details on the content within these domains were not mentioned. Donahue et al. (2019) embedded an adapted flowchart guideline based on the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services' "Framework for a Human Trafficking Protocol in Healthcare Settings" and the Philadelphia Anti-Trafficking Coalition Social Service Subcommittee's treatment guideline. This flowchart evaluation tool offered suggestions for methodically engaging with prospective trafficking victims (Donahue et al., 2019).

Format and Delivery. Several studies conducted their educational intervention in person (Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018), while others were online (Donahue et al., 2019; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). Rheingold et al. (2012) split their participant group into

two, with one group receiving a web-based intervention and the other in-person. The format and delivery of educational interventions included PowerPoint slide decks, handouts, educational scripts, embedded short videos, case studies, and discussions (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012).

Assessment and Measures. Pre- and post-tests with multiple choice, yes or no, true or false questions, and Likert-type scales were administered on paper or electronically (e.g., SurveyMonkey and Qualtrics) to gauge participants' knowledge, beliefs, and satisfaction with the educational session (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012). Participants' demographic data were collected and included questions on years of experience, gender, race/ethnicity, profession, and setting (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012). Outcome measures included recognition and knowledge, retention, and previous education on the topic (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013).

In addition, several studies assessed their participants' confidence in recognizing and treating potential HT victims using Likert Scale questions (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020). Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze all studies' interventions through pre and post-test data (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012).

In the study by McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013), the authors used a randomized control group design to evaluate the webinar training program's effectiveness on CPS participants. The treatment group received CSEC training during the study period, January 2012-February 2012, and completed a questionnaire post-three months. The control group completed

the pretest questionnaire in the first month of the study period, January 2012, completed the follow-up questionnaire in April 2012, and then received the delayed intervention, CSEC training.

Rheingold et al. (2012) also used a randomized control group to evaluate the intervention's effectiveness; however, the authors sought to examine the acceptability and feasibility of in-person versus web-based training. The in-person training occurred during one session, and participants assigned to the web-based training were given two weeks to complete the online training (Rheingold et al., 2012).

Findings. Multiple studies found that participants had little education on CA and trafficking (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz et al., 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012). However, there was a significant increase in participants' knowledge of the post-educational intervention across studies (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). Post-intervention, participants reported more confidence in recognizing and treating potential victims (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020).

In the study by McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013), improvement between the treatment group's pre-and post-test results was statistically significant in the areas of CSEC beliefs ($p < .05$) and knowledge ($p < .01$). Findings between the treatment group and control group three months after the intervention were also statistically significant in the following areas: CSEC scope and demand knowledge ($p < .05$), risk factors ($p < .01$) and CSEC state laws and services ($p < .01$). There were no differences between groups in their ability to define and identify CSEC ($p = .07$), understanding victim behavior ($p = .4$), and the number of children referred to a victim services agency ($p = .06$) (McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013).

The discomfort experienced by web-based and in-person CCP participants during the CSA training was statistically significant ($p=.027$). There were also several differences between the two groups, including that web-based CCP participants expressed more distress than in-person participants when viewing the same footage of adult CSA victims sharing their stories. In contrast to their online counterparts, in-person participants had the opportunity to discuss their post-video reactions with a live facilitator and in a group setting; as a result, in-person participants reported having adequate emotional support resources. Rheingold et al. (2012) recommended adding a response section or setting up an interactive session with a facilitator through live chat to increase participants' feelings of support online.

Another important finding was that compared to online participants, those who attended the course in person reported being likelier to share what they learned with a colleague. Since the in-person training took place within agencies, Rheingold et al. (2012) concluded that it was likely that they were with their coworkers, which encouraged them to want to participate in further conversations.

SN Education

To date, there is limited available research on the effectiveness of training SNs in identifying and treating CSEC/CST victims in the school setting. However, two studies examined the effect of CA education on SNs (Jordan et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017). In the study by Raible et al. (2017), the authors sought to analyze the feasibility of an SN-delivered adolescent relationship abuse (ARA) intervention in the SN's office. The other study examined the effect of CA education interventions on SNs' awareness, knowledge, and confidence levels (Jordan et al., 2017).

Content. The educational content covered in both studies was specific to CA. However, in the study by Raible et al. (2017), education was centered on training SNs to converse with adolescents on healthy versus unhealthy relationships.

CA. The content in the study by Raible et al. (2017) included the impact of ARA on adolescent health, assessment, the process for warm referrals, and healthy and unhealthy relationships, which was provided in a palm-sized brochure that will be supplied to adolescents visiting the SN. Contrarily, the educational content in the study by Jordan et al. (2017) covered child maltreatment, mandatory reporter role, NASN standards, barriers to reporting, risk factors, identification, intervention, and clinical cases, including sexual, emotional, and physical abuse (Jordan et al., 2017). The authors also conducted focus groups with semi-structured interviews in which participants discussed communicating and interacting with affected children and reviewed case scenarios and ethical issues (Jordan et al., 2017).

Format and Delivery. Both studies delivered educational interventions face-to-face (Jordan et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017). Neither study discussed the method of delivery of the content. The educational intervention was provided to 174 SNs from two of the largest school districts in North Carolina in the study by Jordan et al. (2017) and to a core team, 5 of whom were Pennsylvania SNs in the study by Raible et al. (2017).

Assessment and Measures. Pre- and post-test surveys were administered to assess the intervention's effect in both studies (Jordan et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017). SN participants in the study by Raible et al. (2017) took a survey prior to the intervention and a post-survey 10 to 14 months post-implementation. Topics covered included SN's standard operating procedure, protocols, and available ARA resources (Raible et al., 2017). In addition, an anonymous 1-page survey was completed by a convenience sample of 566 students who visited the SN over the

course of two academic years. The content included whether the SN discussed healthy vs. unhealthy relationships, provided the palm-sized interventional brochure, inquired about the usefulness of the information, and whether they shared their personal experiences with unhealthy relationships with the SN (Raible et al., 2017). Both surveys were displayed as frequencies.

In contrast, pre-and post-test surveys analyzed SNs' awareness, confidence, skills, and knowledge in the study by Jordan et al. (2017). The questionnaire was divided into two parts: part one assessed knowledge, and part two assessed confidence and attitudes toward child maltreatment. Part one was composed of multiple-choice questions, and Part two was graded on a 5-point Likert scale. Data collection tools included information about participant demographics such as years of experience, history of receiving child maltreatment education, and the number of children they encountered with suspected or confirmed maltreatment. Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted in both studies to compare pre- and post-intervention effects (Jordan et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017).

Findings. Raible et al. (2017) found that educational resources and ARA resources were more readily available for SNs post-intervention, and all SN participants reported talking about healthy relationships with students. In addition, prompts in students' charts were found to be an effective reminder to initiate ARA discussions. Post-intervention, 96% of student participants reported receiving an ARA educational brochure, and 84% relayed that the information increased their knowledge about how to help someone experiencing ARA and that they engaged in a discussion with their SN. Eighty-five percent of participants agreed that discussing healthy and unhealthy relationships with the SN is helpful, and 83% reported feeling safe in the SN's office (Raible et al., 2017).

Furthermore, a quarter of participants who reported having an unhealthy relationship disclosed it to their SN. There were also differences in exit survey responses among student participants in the first academic year (n=331) of intervention versus the second (n=235), although they were not statistically significant. The authors concluded that the intervention and implementation were effective, feasible, and well-received among SNs and students (Raible et al., 2017).

In the study by Jordan et al. (2017), SN participants' previous formal CA education varied, with only 52% having had some. However, 80% of participants reported caring for a student with suspected or confirmed maltreatment in the past six months (Jordan et al., 2017). A 10% increase in participant knowledge was documented post-educational intervention. An area in which participants answered incorrectly was case scenarios that involved applying their knowledge and making clinical decisions (Jordan et al., 2017). Overall, there was a statistically significant increase in all variables measured by Jordan et al. (2017) post-education session ($p < .01$). Even though the majority of SNs have come into contact with students who are at risk or who have confirmed cases, this study shows that SNs' prior formal education on CA varied. The study indicated that educational sessions effectively increase SN participants' knowledge, attitude, confidence, and self-efficacy (Jordan et al., 2017).

Identified Educational Needs

HT Survivors, HCPs, and Community Members. HT survivors, HCPs, CPS employees, and community member participants identified gaps in education around CA and CSEC/CST, which hindered the ability to identify, recognize, and intervene (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022). A lack of understanding regarding risk factors and red flags,

victim vulnerability, CSEC/CST entry, and involvement indicators, reporting process, and available resources were identified needs (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022).

A situational nature of educational needs was also noted. For instance, the type of training a person requires may depend on where they work, with people in non-metropolitan areas needing more opportunities for awareness-raising and specialized training based on the needs of their communities (Cole & Sprang, 2015; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). Youth HT survivor participants also noted the need for HCPs to have specific training and awareness of the repercussions trafficking has on mental health (Murdock et al., 2022).

SNs. Several studies identified additional educational needs shared by SN participants (Fraley et al., 2018; Jordan et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). Participants expressed uncertainty and discomfort with caring for and making decisions about students suspected to have involvement with or at risk for CSEC/CST (Fraley et al., 2018; Sekhar et al., 2018). Furthermore, SN participants in the study by Kraft et al. (2017) had knowledge and experience with CSA, but their emotions inhibited them from detecting and taking action. Another common theme was vulnerability, attributed to SNs working in silos without school administration support and supervision (Kraft et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017).

However, recommendations such as posting informational pamphlets in plain view in the SN's office, checking for CA or CSEC/CST during required screenings, mentorship, networking, and having access to a screening tool, particularly one with a guide on questions to ask, would not only help to ease their discomfort and uncertainty but also help to normalize these sensitive screenings. (Fraley et al., 2018; Kraft et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017). Additionally, several studies highlighted the necessity of stakeholder buy-in and cooperation between SNs, school

administrators, and community resource organizations like Child Protective Services (CPS) to improve victim support and, in some cases, streamline the reporting process (Jordan et al., 2017; Lutz, 2018; Raible et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018).

Integration of Findings for Educational Module and Selection of Screening Tool

Several studies conducted thematic analyses to identify, analyze, and report patterns among the perspectives of their study participants, which will inform this project (Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley et al., 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Jordan et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022). Several main themes were identified, including beliefs/attitudes, role perceptions, and barriers to reporting. These themes directly impact the identification, intervention, and prevention of CSEC/CST and CA.

Identification

The ability to identify at-risk youth depends on several factors, including the clarity of HCPs' and SNs' role perceptions, recognition of risk factors, and comfort with asking the appropriate questions (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley et al., 2018; Kraft et al., 2017). SN role perceptions regarding CSEC/CST were examined across several studies (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b; Fraley et al., 2018; Kraft et al., 2017). In several studies, SN participants expressed that they should be informed about CA and CSEC/CST, and some believed they should be conducting screenings; however, barriers to doing this included funding, large student caseloads, and time (Fraley et al., 2018; Kraft et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017).

A lack of confidence identified by participants stemmed from limited training, unfamiliarity with risk factors and red flags, unclear reporting guidance, a lack of a screening tool, competing demands, and hesitancy to report without disclosure (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley et al., 2018). In some instances, SNs were aware of risk factors, yet there

was a disconnect when identifying their students and a lack of awareness that exploiters could be other students (Fraley et al., 2018). A shared discomfort in addressing CA and CSEC/CST due to concerns about defensive attitudes among parents and an unease about using specific language (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Kraft et al., 2017). In one study, participants noted that creating language about these screenings as part of standard practice alleviated some angst (Chappell et al., 2021). Additionally, SN participants in the study by Raible et al. (2017) suggested that mandated screenings for vision and hearing would be an excellent time to start a conversation about healthy vs. unhealthy relationships. Several studies also illuminated the SN as the ideal professional to assess for CST/CSEC and CA at school and provide education (Fraley et al., 2018; Gardner et al., 2020; Jordan et al., 2017; Raible et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018).

Intervention

Multiple studies through thematic analysis identified barriers to the intervention across multiple settings (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley et al., 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Hurst et al., 2021; Kraft et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). A lack of time, competing demands, and little confidence in their reporting role due to unclear guidance, insufficient or lack of education and training on screening tools were identified as barriers to reporting (Chappell et al., 2021; Fraley et al., 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017). Furthermore, CSEC/CST survivor participants reported that when SNs questioned them about suspected abuse when they were being trafficked, the questions and terminology used did not correspond to their understanding of their own situation (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a). For example, when asked about their sense of safety, survivors gave affirmative answers, attributing their feelings of safety to not experiencing gun violence or a house fire. Additionally, some participants stated that they were conditioned to lie from a young age to avoid physical

consequences if interrogated, which posed a challenge when answering the SN's questions (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a).

Additional studies identified the need for mandated reporter training and training on identifying CSEC/CST among males (Chappell et al., 2021; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017). Perceptions about the overall effectiveness of reporting and the child welfare system also significantly affected whether HCPs and SNs decided to report (Chappell et al., 2021; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017). A lack of collaboration and communication regarding follow-up after an HCP or SN filed a report to CPS increased their uncertainty in the overall process (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Hurst et al., 2021; Kraft et al., 2017). However, Kraft et al. (2017) noted a correlation between the years of SN experience working with vulnerable children and taking accountability for reporting, specifically, the ability to trust their instincts. Furthermore, McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013) suggest that policies are developed to specify the number of red flags that should warrant further investigation or referrals.

Prevention

Participants across multiple studies expressed their beliefs and attitudes about CA and CSEC/CST. For many, these were considered taboo topics, highly stigmatized, and painful to discuss (Chappell et al., 2021; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017). Others believed CST was not a domestic problem in their communities (Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley et al., 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017). Although these beliefs and attitudes have halted or hindered previous prevention efforts, participants reported that training, mentorship, and partnerships between school and community stakeholders, including CPS and domestic violence

agencies, would alleviate barriers (Chappell et al., 2021; Jordan et al., 2017; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Raible et al., 2017).

Conclusion

This review of the literature highlighted several gaps in CA and CSEC/CST identification, screening, and reporting due to a lack of HCP and SN knowledge, awareness, and perceptions. Although a limited number of peer-reviewed studies in the U.S. address CSEC, especially in the school setting, this review helped to broaden CA and CSEC knowledge and identification by exploring additional practice settings. Multiple studies provided firsthand accounts of HCPs, SNs, and HT survivors, which addressed shortcomings and missed opportunities and helped to inform future practice.

Evidence-based training can support the early identification of CA, including CSEC/CST, which not only protects children at risk but can significantly improve a community's overall health, which supports this project's underlying framework, the SEM (Chappell et al., 2021; Gardner et al., 2020). However, education alone is insufficient in addressing CA and CSEC/CST without instilling a practice change (Lutz, 2018; Murdock et al., 2022). This project provided SN participants with the knowledge and skills to detect, manage, and prevent CSEC/CST across educational settings and a tangible, evidence-based screening tool to identify at-risk students- a concrete first step toward changing SN practice.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to develop an evidence-based HT educational module, inclusive of CST, tailored to California (CA) SNs for use in their school settings and sought SN participants' input on a validated CST screening tool. The SEM directed the creation of the educational module and selection of the validated tool because it offered a comprehensive understanding of how CSEC/CST relates to a child's personal, relational, social, and environmental contexts (CDC, 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020).

Although NASN and CSNO have adopted HT position statements, neither group has suggested a standardized trafficking tool that SNs can use (CSNO, 2022; NASN, 2021). Despite growing awareness of HT, nurses in all specialties have limited training (Peck & Doiron, 2022). For SNs, a deficiency in appropriate HT education and knowledge results in uncoordinated and ineffective responses in the school environment (Doiron & Peck, 2022). If equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills, and a practical screening tool, SNs can significantly impact the lives of children at risk for HT.

The specific objectives were to a) assess the level of HT awareness among CA SNs; b) create an educational module addressing any knowledge gaps; c) collaborate with the CSNO State Board to distribute pre-surveys to all CSNO members on their listserv; d) distribute the educational module to all CSNO members who indicated an interest in the initial survey; e) elicit feedback on a validated evidence-based CST screening tool; and f) distribute post-surveys to assess the module's effect on participant's level of awareness of and attitudes about CSEC/CST.

Sample and Study Design

Participation was open to all current CSNO members who were listserv subscribers for the State Board; as a result, the project's sample was a convenience sample. At the time of the

project's initial phase, in October 2023, there were approximately 1,700 active CSNO members across all six sections. All participant data was de-identified and discussed as aggregate data. This project assessed SN participants' perceptions of CSEC/CST before and after the educational intervention without using a control group and will employ a pre/post-test design (Grove, 2019a).

Setting

CSNO was founded in 1950 by two SNs in Los Angeles and Orange counties and currently serves as the only SN professional organization in California (CSNO, 2023a). Today, the organization consists of six sections: 1) Bay Coast, 2) Central Coast, 3) Central Valley, 4) Northern, 5) San Diego-Imperial, and 6) Southern (CSNO, 2023b). The organization has state and regional section boards that work together to provide support, networking, and professional development (CSNO, 2023b).

This doctoral project took place within a virtual context with the support of CSNO's State board. Due to the technical nature of this project, several extraneous variables may have influenced the project's overall outcome. These include time constraints and accessibility (i.e., reliable Internet, computer access, and CSNO email listserv) of CSNO SN participants.

Measures

Participant demographic data was collected; the response format for these questions included selecting all that apply and yes or no responses. The data was reported as categorical data and represented as a percentage (Appendix K, Table 1).

Operational Definitions

The basic building blocks of a theory are constructs, which are ideas with a broad meaning but are complex and can include multiple concepts (Gray, 2019). Variables in research

represent these operationally and conceptually defined concepts. The operational definition explains how the concept or variable will be measured or controlled, whereas the conceptual definition gives a variable's theoretical meaning (Grove, 2019b).

For this project, SNs' attitudes, awareness, knowledge, perceptions, and educational effectiveness were operationalized using a pre-and post-survey with Likert-type questions. The survey link and QR code were embedded in a CSNO email announcement, on a PowerPoint slide presented at CSNO fall section conferences, and during a CSNO virtual happy hour event. The survey was administered through Qualtrics. A Likert scale is an ordinal scale with 5 or 7 points on which responses can be rated or ranked numerically according to agreement or disagreement with the stated statement (e.g., "always," "often," "agree," "neutral") (Sullivan & Artino, 2013). The SNAPS survey uses a 5-point Likert scale to describe and measure these variables. Higher scores correspond to greater awareness, attitudes, and perceptions of one's role in CSEC (Fraley et al., 2018).

Attitudes. A person's attitude is how they unconsciously or consciously assess or evaluate a particular phenomenon, either favorably or unfavorably (Klaver et al., 2021). SN attitudes were measured using an attitudes subscale that measured CSEC pathways/precursors and victim identification (Fraley et al., 2018). This scale, which had 16 items, examined SNs' perceptions of students who were at risk for CSEC with Likert scale questions (Fraley et al., 2018).

Awareness. Awareness is a concept that refers to the state of knowing (Coolen et al., 2019). Awareness about a phenomenon can inform one's practice and help one develop their roles and responsibilities (Marková et al., 2006; Rasheed et al., 2018). Three areas of awareness were examined in the SNAPS survey: the definition of CSEC, its impact, and student

vulnerability (Fraley et al., 2018). Student vulnerability encompassed whether SNs were aware of personal and societal risk factors.

CSEC knowledge was assessed by McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013) through the pre-and post-intervention questionnaire. Knowledge was measured by examining whether the study participants were able to 1) identify and define CSEC; 2) aware of CSEC demand and scope; 3) identify CSEC entry risk factors; 4) aware of CSEC victim behavior; 5) aware of laws and services for CSEC; 6) had screening question knowledge; and 7) were willing to participate in the referral process (McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). These categories were addressed using a true or false statement format, and the variable was quantified using coding (e.g., 1=correct answer). A higher score was associated with greater knowledge (McMahon-Howard & Reimers., 2013).

Role Perceptions. Perception is a multifaceted, individualized construct that encompasses how one views the world through stimuli and past experiences and is influenced by various sociocultural factors (McDonald, 2012). Since perception is an individual's perspective, it can motivate action (McDonald, 2012). Role perceptions were measured by looking at SNs' perceptions of their role in engaging and identifying victims of CSEC (Fraley et al., 2018).

Effectiveness. Effectiveness is a concept that can be used to assess whether an intervention or initiative resulted in a desired outcome or effect based on planned objectives or goals; the unit of analysis is the output measure (Burches & Burches, 2020; Hinrichs-Krapels & Grant, 2016). In the study by McMahon-Howard and Reimers (2013), the effectiveness of a CSEC training program for CPS employees was measured by comparing the results of pre- and post-intervention questionnaires, specifically on the topic of CSEC beliefs. A 5-point Likert scale was used to quantify CSEC belief statements, with “1” equating to “strongly disagree” and “5” to

“strongly agree.” A code of 1 was given to all “strongly agree” answers, with higher scores denoting stronger pro-CSEC beliefs (McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). Strong pro-CSEC beliefs were defined as participants who viewed children involved in CSEC as victims instead of criminal offenders (McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013). The authors hypothesized that training would change participants’ beliefs about CSEC.

Types of Measures

Process. Process measures lead to the project’s desired outcome (Provost & Murray, 2022). This project's process measure included feedback from SN participants on CSEC knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions, which was measured through the analysis of pre-survey open-ended responses and Likert-scale results. Answers informed knowledge gaps that were addressed in the educational module. For this project, this process measure depended on a sufficient sample size determined by a power analysis (Bootland et al., 2017).

Outcome. Outcome measures are related to the system’s performance, offer evidence that changes impact the system level, and represent the patient's or customer's voice (Provost & Murray, 2022). The outcome measures for this project included 1) the percentage of SN participants who reported increased awareness, perceptions, and knowledge of CSEC/CST as a result of the educational module and 2) the percentage of SN participants who reported increased confidence in their ability to identify, intervene and prevent CSEC/CST because of the educational module. These measures were quantified through the post-survey questionnaire and reported as a percentage.

Balancing. Balancing measures detect whether changes in one area negatively affect the process in another (Provost & Murray, 2022). Several balancing measures were considered in this project. The introduction of an educational module and screening tool added to SNs’ already

heavy workload which could have led to hesitancy of SNs to be open to this project. There is also a possibility that the recommended screening tool favors sensitivity over specificity, leading to many false positives, but the trade-off is warranted (Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Hurst et al., 2021).

Pre- and Post-Survey Instruments

The pre-and post-survey instruments used in this project with SN participants were a combination of three instruments specially tailored to fit the project's focus: CSEC/CST. An adapted version of a tool developed by Jordan et al. (2017) was used to evaluate the attitudes and confidence of SN participants. The original instrument was used to gauge the SN participants' self-reported knowledge, confidence, and skills concerning child maltreatment. Although the tool's reliability and validity were not reported, the authors reported that the tool was reviewed by expert nurses, physicians, and a nurse-research content expert for reliability and validity of content (Jordan et al., 2017). Several survey questions were also drawn from Donahue et al.'s (2019) tool that was used initially to assess ED personnel's confidence levels in their ability to identify and treat HT victims presenting to their department and the usefulness of the educational module (Donahue et al., 2019). These tools informed the pre- and post-survey as shown in Appendix G.

The final instrument, which was not be used in its entirety, was the SNAPS for Youth At-Risk of Trafficking as shown in Appendix F). This 32-item tool was developed and validated by Fraley and Aronowitz (2021b) to measure SN attitudes and perceptions of CSEC and their perceived roles in prevention. The tool consists of three subscales (risk awareness, attitudes, and role perceptions) in a 5-point Likert scale format. The overall score ranges from 32-160, with higher scores denoting higher levels of knowledge and more optimistic attitudes and perceptions

(Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b). The authors concluded that in both study phases (exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis), SNAPs had strong psychometric properties and is a valid and reliable tool to measure SNs' attitudes and awareness of students at risk for CSEC. The findings indicate that the final tool has good internal consistency ($\alpha = .94$) and test-retest reliability of .91 (Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b).

Educational Module

The literature review, including the SEM and participants' knowledge gaps identified in the pre-survey results, was used to develop the educational module. The module was pre-recorded with a voiceover on PowerPoint and delivered to SN participants who indicated an interest in receiving the module during the pre-survey. Modular content included: 1) types of HT, 2) HT federal and state laws, 3) CSEC vulnerabilities, entry points, risk factors, and red flags, 4) health implications, 5) CSEC presentation in the school setting, 6) NASN and CSNO HT position statements, 7) trauma-informed care, 8) Greenbaum et al. (2018)'s 6-item screening tool (see Appendix M), 9) barriers to identification, 10) reporting requirements and considerations, 11) national and state resources, 12) supplementary materials (e.g., training, protocol development, specific population considerations) and 13) self-care resources. The module also included hyperlinks to real case examples from Polaris, the Federal Bureau of Investigation, and other U.S. governmental agencies. The case examples were chosen to provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of ST's complexity and to encourage them to apply their knowledge to real-world scenarios.

Data Collection

Data was collected by the principal investigator using Qualtrics, a data abstraction tool. Data protection was ensured since all data was stored on the principal investigator (PI)'s

password-protected laptop in a locked office. No information was uploaded to the Cloud. The project's timeline is outlined in a table as shown in Appendix H. There is no pre-existing data at this time, so the development and distribution of a pre-survey was needed to establish baseline data of SN participants.

Methods for Evaluation

Data analysis reports were produced using QI Macros, a statistical program, and Microsoft Excel. For this project, participants' attitudes, awareness, knowledge, perceptions about HT, and the overall effectiveness of the educational module were operationalized using a pre-and post-survey with Likert-type questions. For data analysis, questions with answers marked 1, 2, or 3 were collapsed and operationalized as unaware or negative attitudes and responses with a 4 or 5 were deemed aware or having a positive attitude. SN participants' attitudes were assessed using an attitudes subscale incorporating CSEC pathways/precursors, victim identification, and role perceptions. The survey assessed SN participants' awareness of HT definitions, societal and personal risk factors, and student-specific factors (e.g., mental health diagnoses, social-emotional status, familial relationships, etc.). Descriptive statistics were used to describe participant and school-setting demographics as shown in Appendix K, Table 1.

Plan for Tool Rollout

Although this project did not include fully implementing the recommended tool, the plan for a future rollout involves several recommendations. Distribution of a double-sided finalized evidence-based tool on one side and screening guidance on the other (e.g., questions to ask and red flags) in a PDF format that can be laminated should be provided to SNs. In addition, it is recommended that an electronic survey be sent to all CSNO listserv members specific to tool usage. Survey questions should be geared toward measuring whether the tool is being used

correctly, in what capacity, and the number of identified and reported cases. Future outcome measures should include 1) the rate of SN participants using the tool appropriately and 2) the percentage of students flagged due to screening.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional review board (IRB) approval was obtained from California State University, Fullerton as shown in Appendix I. The project was deemed exempt because there was no foreseen risk to patients and little to no risk to SN participants. Informed consent was obtained for both the pre- and post-survey. Due to the topic's sensitive nature, additional information about support resources was available in the educational module. Data on participant responses were gathered, de-identified, and reported as aggregate data. Additionally, CSNO provided the PI with a written letter of support as shown in Appendix E.

Results

Quantitative Findings

The study's participants were current CSNO members who were also active SNs and over the age of 18. Appendix K, Table 1 summarizes the descriptive data of pre- and post-survey participants.

Pre-Survey

Participant Characteristics. A total of 230 CSNO members responded to the pre-survey, and 155 answered all of the required questions, yielding an overall response rate of 67.39%. The majority were White females (70.97%), followed by Asian (9.68%), and were not Hispanic or Latino (85.16%), from the Southern Section (28.39%), with an age range of 41 to 60 with less than five years of SN experience (36.77%). Four of the participants were men, and one declined to state. A little more than half reported having a bachelor's (50.32%) or master's (40%), and a small percentage reported having a doctorate (3.23%). Close to 6% reported having an additional certificate or credential, of which 66.66% specifically stated that they possess a SN credential.

School Setting Characteristics. The majority of respondents reported working across grade levels (40.65%), assigned ≥ 4 schools (31.61%), and over 88% worked in traditional public schools. One-third of participants worked in suburban settings, with nearly 20% reported working in rural areas. Six participants indicated they worked outside the school setting in their respective county offices of education. Participants were asked how many students they were responsible for in their SN role; only completed responses to the open-ended question were analyzed (N=140). The range was 0 to 95,000, with an average of 3,463 students.

Student-Specific Factors, School Community, and HT. The majority (87.10%) oversaw the care of both special (SPED) and general education (gen ed) students, with 5% solely responsible for SPED students. Most respondents (33.55%) reported that their schools had \geq 75% minority enrollment and that crime was somewhat of a concern in their areas (60.65%). Most respondents (56.77%) have previously received some form of HT education, and fourteen (9.03%) indicated that they had encountered a victim of HT in their school. Eighty percent of participants indicated that they had previously completed a CPS report, and one reported calling the HT hotline while working as a SN. Eighty-six percent (N=130) also indicated an interest in receiving the educational module and post-survey.

Post-Survey

Initial recruitment for the post-survey yielded few responses, necessitating four email reminders in one month and extending the deadline by 10 days.

Participant Characteristics. Fifty of the 59 respondents who accessed the post-survey answered all the required questions, with a response rate of 84.74%. Forty-nine, or 98%, were female, with one declining to disclose their gender. The majority (58%) were \geq 51 years old, White (78%), followed by Asian (10%), and not Hispanic or Latino (92%). In addition, most respondents were from the Southern Section (26%), held master's degrees (46%), and had \geq 21 years of SN experience (30%). Three respondents (6%) had doctorates, and five (10%) reported having a SN credential.

School Setting Characteristics. Similar to the pre-survey, most post-survey respondents (36%) were assigned \geq 4 schools. They worked predominantly in public schools (90%) and suburban settings (56%). Three participants reported working for their county offices of education. As with the pre-survey, only completed responses were used to establish the average

number of pupils for which SN participants (N=46) were accountable. The range was 50-74,000, with an average of 3,358.

Student-Specific Factors, School Community, and HT. Like the pre-survey, respondents predominately oversaw the care of special and general education students (84%) across multiple grade levels (46%). Unlike pre-survey respondents, most post-survey participants (N=40) reported working at schools with 25-49% minority enrollment, and 28% reported that crime was not a problem in their community. Thirty-one participants (62%) indicated that they had never received HT education, 28% were unsure whether they had encountered a victim of HT in the school setting (N=14), five (10%) reported they had, and 90% had filed a CPS report in the past (N=45). None of the post-survey participants indicated that they called the HT Hotline while working as an SN.

Awareness and Attitudes Assessment

For this project, SNs' awareness and attitudes were operationalized using a pre-and post-survey with 5-point Likert scale questions using an Attitudes and Awareness assessment. For data analysis, questions with answers marked 1, 2, or 3 were collapsed and categorized as unaware or negative attitudes, and responses with a 4 or 5 as aware or having a positive attitude. It is worth noting that the pre- and post-survey sample sizes were unequal. However, given that this was a descriptive study, the data explored remains of value. The key findings are summarized below.

Awareness. The results of the awareness subscale are presented in two sections: student-related risk factors and ST.

Student-related Risk Factors. The majority of respondents, both in the pre- and post-survey, were aware of their students' familial relationships (57.42% and 62%, respectively),

social-emotional status (74.84% and 76%), mental health diagnoses (78.71% and 86%), and students residing in foster care or DCFS custody (66.35% and 76%). Pre-survey respondents were more familiar with their students' peer relationships (58.71%) than those in the post-survey (48%).

Sex Trafficking. Most pre-survey respondents (57.42%) were unfamiliar with the term CSEC, whereas 78% of post-survey respondents were. Similarly, most pre-survey respondents (71.61%) reported being unaware of exploiters' control and coercion methods, a percentage that dropped considerably in the post-survey to 30%.

Attitudes. The results of respondents' attitudes are examined in three sections: student-related risk factors, attitudes toward ST, and the role of the SN.

Student-related Risk Factors. Most respondents (89.68% pre-survey and 96% post-survey) believed students could be CSEC victims. Furthermore, 82.58% of pre-survey and 94% of post-survey participants also felt that students could be exploiters of HT. When asked about their attitudes toward the relationship between CSEC and CSA, more than 90% of pre- and post-survey respondents agreed that there was one. Most participants (83.23% pre- and 94% post-survey) also believed there was a link between CSEC and poverty.

Sex Trafficking. Most respondents in both the pre- and post-surveys agreed that ST is an issue nationally (69.68% and 86%) and in their respective communities (96.77% and 98%). Slightly more than half of pre-survey respondents (56.13%) indicated they had an inadequate understanding of ST, whereas most post-survey respondents (88%) did.

When asked about their confidence in their ability to identify 1) at-risk children, 2) suspected cases, 3) high-risk situations and red flags, and 4) initiate interventions for a child suspected of CSEC involvement, the majority of pre-survey respondents expressed a lack of

confidence (79.35%, 80%, 63.87%, and 72.26%, respectively). On the contrary, post-survey participants reported increased confidence in the abovementioned categories (52%, 54%, 72%, and 66%). Furthermore, most pre-survey participants (60.65%) reported being uncomfortable asking a child questions about CSEC, which fell to 36% in the post-survey.

Role Perceptions. Respondents were asked whether they believed knowing about CSEC in their SN role was essential. More than 95% of participants thought it was (97.42% pre- and 96% post-survey). Furthermore, 72.26% of pre- and 90% of post-survey respondents believed that screening for CSEC was within their SN's scope. Most pre- and post-survey participants reported knowing what to do as a mandated reporter if they suspected CSEC in their school setting (72.90% and 94%).

More than 75% of respondents (78.06% pre- and 82% post-survey) reported that knowledge is a barrier to identifying CSEC as a SN. When asked if SNs had access to appropriate educational materials to increase their understanding of CSEC, most pre-survey participants (57.42%) disagreed. However, over half of the post-survey participants (60%) agreed. Additionally, 94.84% of pre- and 94% of post-survey respondents indicated a willingness to participate in educational opportunities to learn their role as a SN in CSEC prevention. A summary of pre- and post-survey results can be found in Appendix L, Table 2.

CST Screening Tool Feedback

Post-survey participants were provided with Greenbaum et al. 's 6-item screening tool, incorporated in the educational module. Participants were asked whether this tool would be appropriate in their work settings. Most (92%) felt it was appropriate, 6% were unsure, and one participant noted it was not (Appendix O).

Qualitative Findings: Open-Ended Survey Questions

Pre- and post-survey respondents were presented with two open-text field responses to the following statements: 1) please list any barriers you see to identifying CSEC in your role as a school nurse, and 2) please write any comments or questions that you have about CSEC.

SN Barriers to CSEC Identification

Ninety-five pre-survey and 30 post-survey participants provided information on the barriers to identifying CSEC in their settings; a Word cloud was generated to capture the themes (Appendix P). The most common obstacles are reported below.

Time. The most reported barrier by survey respondents was time. This included the time to attend training and screen for CSEC and the opportunity for 1:1 time with students. Many participants stated that being assigned to multiple schools or working in district offices reduced their time with students, making it challenging to create trusting relationships. Some of the responses included:

“I have multiple school sites, I do not sit in one place very long and therefore, unless there is a medical reason to really know a student, I just don't have enough exposure with them to garner trust.”

“I have 4 school sites and not being able to spend extended time at a school is a hinderance [*sic*] to identifying students who are at risk of CSEC.”

“The amount of foot traffic in my office gives me little time to spend on students, especially when there is a health emergency or acute situation.”

“Since I'm at multiples [*sic*] sites, I lack opportunities to have a continuous, trusting relationships with students and also likelihood of noticing signs that a student might be involved in CSEC.”

Large Caseloads. Many respondents cited that their high-volume caseloads were another impediment, stating that, similar to a lack of time, heavy caseloads prohibited them from developing relationships with students and limited their ability to identify potential red flags.

“Separate school sites to cover can limit exposure to students to prevent rapport/relationship so student can trust nursing staff.”

“I feel so spread thin between two schools. When you are only at each school 10 days a month it’s hard to get to know the social dynamics, families and students so it is harder to identify or screen for a lot of things.”

“The caseload of school nurses prevents school nurses from having more intimate relationships with students. They are often rushed to move onto the next student, procedure or meeting.”

“High number of students/schools makes it difficult to focus on individual student's needs.”

Lack of Knowledge. Respondents also noted that a lack of access to high-quality education, ongoing training, and limited resources and opportunities for professional development all contribute to the lack of SN knowledge about CSEC. Without sufficient training, SN respondents reported being unable to recognize red flags and what actions to take if CSEC was suspected.

“Knowledge of how to identify CSEC at my school. Knowledge of what things to look out for, what questions to ask, and what immediate next steps to take.”

“I’m not sure where to refer or how to report CSEC.”

Lack of Awareness. Respondents highlighted a lack of CSEC awareness among their SN colleagues, district leadership, and parents as a barrier to CSEC identification. Some of the responses are noted below.

“Very conservative district and leadership that doesn't acknowledge that sex trafficking exists and could happen to some of our students.”

“Simply put, many don't want to talk about CSEC and don't believe it can happen in 'their part of town' or 'to their children that they serve'. School Boards are pressured by the vocal minority to 'not talk about such unpleasant things' and often encourage Districts to 'leave well enough alone' and not offer PD on CSEC.”

“An unknown need to know this information.”

SN Role. The root of this barrier was bias among school administrators, staff, and parents due to their lack of understanding of the SN's role in CSEC screening. Several respondents reported that administrators and others believe CSEC falls under the umbrella of mental health, not physical health, thus assuming that school counselors and psychologists are best suited to manage suspected CSEC cases. For instance:

“Advised by administration to "stay in my lane" and only address health issues.”

“I work within a Wellness Center where other service providers may identify CSEC and not make a referral to the school nurse.”

“Being included by other school team members. As the emphasis shifts to mental health on campuses, I feel much of my role and ability as a school nurse being siloed off to strictly "physical health" and I am not thought of as a potential valuable resource in this area.”

“I also do not feel school administrators and parents would feel it is the role of school nurses to screen students. More education and school policies that support this would be required.”

Students. According to several respondents, students’ own mistrust or inability to disclose sensitive information to their SN is another barrier.

“School Nurses are also notorious for inflicting their personal values on situations at work and judgement [*sic*] oozes off many SN so students simply don't connect, feel safe or share what their personal reality is.”

“Students will hide it the best they can, so the more staff that are trained the better.

Teachers should also be trained with the tool. Sometimes the students confide in a certain teacher and are hesitant to come to the health office.”

“Students being unwilling to discuss a potentially questionable situation.”

Other Barriers. Additional barriers identified by respondents included: 1) their lack of a CSEC screening tool; 2) hesitance by other SNs to implement a screening tool; 3) non-verbal and SPED populations; 4) language barriers; 5) fear of re-traumatization; 6) the lack of private safe spaces for student disclosure; 7) unfamiliarity with their SN role if CSEC is suspected; and 8) complicity of district personnel. One respondent noted, “I believe I lost my job in a previous district due to suspected CSEC and complicity of district employees.”

CSEC Questions and Comments

Participants were provided an open-text field to respond to the statement, “[p]lease write any comments or questions that you have about CSEC.” Twenty-two pre- and nine post-survey participants provided questions or comments. More than half of the pre-survey participants were

interested in learning more about CSEC, including specifics on prevalence, resources, screening tools, and a general need to know more. Some examples included:

“Where can we obtain resources and screening tools?”

“How do I find out more information related to my county?”

“[A]lthough this is a very hot topic around the country and world, there is not much discussion and exposure for nurses regarding education to build knowledge about the topic.”

“I would like opportunities to learn more about CSEC and how I can help stop it.”

“This is a great project! We all need to be educated and confident in identifying and reporting.”

“It would be great if there could be sessions about SCEC [*sic*] at the next CSNO Conference.”

Additionally, some post-survey respondents expressed an increased awareness of the necessity of a HT protocol, the HT hotline, and knowledge about the average age of CST victims.

“I would want to know what our local police do and expect from us. Does CPS collaborate with police in a timely manner? Would the trafficker retaliate? All of these questions tell me that I need to write a protocol for our nurses so they do not feel scared to engage in this kind of assessment. When we feel empowered, we are confident.”

“I didn’t know there was a hotline.”

“It's shocking and appalling that typical age range for human trafficking in the USA is 11-14.”

CST Screening Tool Feedback

Post-survey respondents were asked whether they had additional input regarding Greenbaum et al.'s CST screening tool, including any revisions or additions specific to school nursing. Twenty-five (50%) of respondents offered feedback. Several themes emerged, and they included: 1) developmental appropriateness, 2) multidisciplinary coordination, 3) parental concerns, 4) policies, procedures, and protocol development, 5) education, and 6) usefulness.

Developmental Appropriateness. Four respondents stated that the tool was appropriate for middle and high school students, but not younger, because of the sensitive content and degree of understanding required to respond to the questions. One participant had the following response:

“Greenbaum's 6-item screening tool seems more appropriate for middle and high school students. I have 4 elementary sites. I'm not sure that the tool will be very useful with elementary population. However, I can see some questions I can derive from the tool to make it more appropriate for younger children.”

Multidisciplinary Collaboration. Three participants highlighted the need for multidisciplinary collaboration regarding screening with other school personnel, including guidance counselors and psychologists. Some of the responses included:

“I could see this being more appropriate for a school psychologist. I wonder if there is something less sensitive that could be an initial screening by a school nurse and then trigger a referral to a school psychologist.”

“I wonder how to coordinate with the school's guidance counselor, psychologist, etc.”

Although several respondents alluded to the necessity of collaboration, one pointed out that by requesting the SN to screen and report to CPS, teachers are essentially “passing the buck.”

Parental Concerns. Several respondents anticipated strong resistance to CST screening by parents since they worked in conservative districts and those where parents were heavily involved.

“The question about how many sexual partners a student has had may be difficult to ask in our very conservative district. Parents complain about everything and this may appear too explicit and intrusive.”

“I could see very negative responses from parents if it is used universally.”

“I work for a Charter School and we do not even participate in the Healthy Kids Survey because of parent protest. I don't think our administration and board would support using the tool widely.”

One respondent expressed that the ability to use the tool without parental resistance is situational, noting that “[s] schools with lower family involvement would be able to implement this easier than schools with intense parental involvement.”

Policies, Procedures, and Protocols. Respondents also indicated the necessity for clear guidelines and protocols regarding screening for CSEC. Some responses included questions and statements about who should be screened, conditions that necessitate using the tool, guidance on positive screens, and whether parental consent and notification are needed. Another question posed by a respondent concerned whether identifying red flags in a student's life is sufficient or if a district policy is required for screening.

“I do think it is a good and important screen, but there would need to be clear policies and parameters around its use.”

“We have many short encounters with a lot of students throughout the day. I am not sure that this would be useful for every encounter. Maybe I would want to establish a protocol to determine when it would be used.”

“Provide clear parameters/indicators for use and/or information on parental/guardian consent or notification.”

Education. Several respondents expressed that the screening tool should be used alongside education for SNs, students, and unlicensed assistive personnel. Furthermore, one respondent indicated that the instructions when administering the tool should be clear and simple.

“This tool would need to be combined with a lot of education to students.”

“I recommend that all steps are made very clear as the person administering the screening will want very black and white guidance. They may be stressed by the child's report and the person administering the screening may become confused if the steps are not simple and specific.”

Usefulness. Several participants recognized that the screening tool would not only enhance their understanding of CSEC indicators but also assist them in their overall job,

“I really like the idea of having a tool to help with my job. I work in a rural district and have experienced some strange occurrences that lead me to believe trafficking is happening in my area. This tool would be very helpful.”

“It is very helpful to learn about the tool and be better informed about signs to look for.”

“The questions include examples of the behaviors that the respondent is being asked to self-report. This is a fantastic feature in these questions as many teens default to 'what does that mean' or 'I don't know what you mean' and by including examples in the

question they can ponder the question thoroughly without the School Nurse filling the silence trying to explain the question.”

Educational Module Feedback

Post-survey participants asked whether they had anything else to add since completing the educational module. Twenty-one (84%) respondents provided their input, expressing an interest in ongoing training and the need for more discourse on this issue. Some examples included the following:

“Things change, methods change and I think we should constantly be educated about CSEC.”

“I would love to see more training in this area, with concrete examples of what to look for, and scenarios on how to approach interviewing students and intervening if appropriate.”

“PRAY this topic becomes heavily presented throughout California and ALL school districts. The more you know, the more you can help!”

“Thank you for the opportunity to learn about human trafficking that may be happening in my schools. I feel slightly better equipped to be able to identify and help these children.”

“This is uncomfortable for a majority of professionals to discuss...[y]ou have opened eyes and started a necessary conversation.”

“... [i]t was also enlightening to think about labor trafficking and consider my community. I live not far from one of the "hubs" in California. This was shocking!”

Discussion

California has one of the highest rates of HT nationwide (Human Rights Center, 2024). The average age of victims of CST is between 11 and 14, or school age (Office of the Attorney General, 2017). Research indicates that schools serve as both a place where victims attend as well as recruitment hubs for traffickers, including other students (Fraley et al., 2018; Grace et al., 2012; NASN, 2021). As one of the only HCPs with access to and interaction with students on an individual basis in this educational environment, SNs are well-positioned and have an obligation to identify, address, and prevent CST (CSNO, 2022; NASN, 2021).

Employing quantitative and qualitative methods, this DNP project, informed by peer-reviewed literature and pre-survey participants, included the development of an evidence-based HT module, inclusive of CST, designed explicitly for California SNs. Additionally, the project sought post-survey participants' feedback on a validated CST screening tool that could be used in SN practice. The specific objectives of this project were to a) assess the level of HT awareness among CA SNs, b) create an educational module addressing any knowledge gaps, c) collaborate with the CSNO State Board to distribute pre-surveys to all CSNO members on their listserv, d) distribute the educational module to all CSNO members who indicated an interest in the initial survey, e) elicit feedback on a validated evidence-based CST screening tool and f) distribute post-surveys to assess the module's effect on participant's level of awareness of and attitudes about CSEC/CST.

Data were collected through participants' pre- and post-survey results. A word cloud and exemplar quotes were used to depict the qualitative data analysis, while tables and graphs were used to explain the quantitative data analysis. The significant findings of this project not only corroborate the paucity of research focused on SNs and their role in CST identification,

intervention, prevention, and education but also shed new light on the feasibility of a validated CST screening tool that has yet to be used in the educational setting.

Interpreting Results through the SEM Lens

The development of the Awareness and Attitudes Assessment, educational module, and selection of the recommended CST tool was guided by the SEM since this conceptual framework provided a comprehensive lens to view the intricate relationship between a student's individual, relational, social, and environmental characteristics, and CSEC/CST (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Kilanowski, 2017; Peck, 2020). According to the project's findings, SN participants' knowledge, awareness, perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs regarding CST and their role in the identification, screening, prevention, and education efforts varied. The findings are discussed within the project's guiding framework, the SEM.

Individual (Student)

According to the SEM, the individual level includes biological factors and personal history that influence whether an individual can become an aggressor or victim (CDC, 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). As documented in the literature, poor academic performance, individuals with disabilities, certain minority groups, foster youth, and those with mental health vulnerabilities are at increased risk for victimization (Ellis et al., 2022; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Fraley et al., 2018; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Greenbaum et al., 2018b; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017).

Study participants were asked specific questions concerning the individual or student level, including if they were aware of or familiar with the socioemotional status, mental health diagnoses, and foster or DCFS custody status of their students (Appendix L, Table 2). Additionally, they were asked about grade level, student population type (i.e., Gen Ed vs.

SPED), and the percentage of enrolled minority students. A significant proportion of participants, both pre-and post-survey, were aware of their students' socio-emotional status and mental health diagnoses, as well as those in foster care or DCFS custody. Along with caring for both gen ed and SPED students, the majority of respondents also reported that their student population consisted of at least $\geq 25\%$ of minority enrollment. One post-survey participant also highlighted the necessity of CSEC education for students, a point raised by participants in Sekhar et al.'s (2018) study, and it is also one of the CDC's targeted preventative strategies at this level (2022).

Although many participants noted their heavy caseloads, multiple school site assignments, and lack of time hindered their ability to build trusting relationships with students and notice potential red flags, an encouraging key finding was that SN participants seemed to be generally aware of their students' individual risk factors. Having this awareness is an essential first step in identifying students at-risk for or victims of CST.

Relationship

An individual's inner circle, particularly close relationships that could place them at a higher risk of suffering violence, is examined at this level (CDC, 2022; Peck, 2020). SN participants were asked about their familiarity with their students' peer and familial relationships. The findings suggest that while most pre- and post-survey respondents were aware of their students' familial relationships, pre-survey respondents were more aware of their students' peer relationships than post-survey respondents.

One explanation could be that SNs prioritize students' health and well-being, necessitating contact with a student's parents or guardians for general care (i.e., medication administration and specialized health care procedures), health screenings, and emergencies

(CSNO, 2023a). These interactions often give SNs a deeper insight into a student's family dynamics. Unexpectedly, the participants' level of awareness in both types of relationships varied from 48 to 62%, which is an encouraging discovery considering that SN participants reported having limited time at a given school and infrequent one-on-one encounters with students.

Future studies might investigate the extent of SNs' awareness of a student's home environment, including factors such as poverty, unstable housing, substance misuse, and domestic violence (Barnert et al., 2017; Cole, 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; McMahon-Howard & Reimers., 2013; Murdock et al., 2022). Additionally, SNs' understanding of familial and peer associations in the sex trade should be explored since these factors heighten the risk for CST victimization (Austin et al., 2020; Cole, 2018; Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020).

Community/School

This project primarily focused on the school community, specifically SNs. Research notes that at this level, children can be heavily influenced by their school environment, and their development and risk for victimization can be impacted (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Peck, 2020). Supportive school environments and a sense of community are protective factors for vulnerable youth (Butler et al., 2022). Several studies highlight the significant role SNs play in helping at-risk students, particularly when SNs are aware of their roles and responsibilities and have the tools (i.e., training and protocols) to do so (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021a; Grace et al., 2012; Reisner et al., 2020). Thus, having a trusted SN who is equipped with the knowledge and skills to identify, intervene, and prevent CSEC/CST is essential.

Specific questions regarding the participant's school community, such as crime and prior interactions with victims of HT and if ST is an issue in their community, were posed to

participants (Appendix K, Table 1). Additionally, participants were asked about their level of knowledge regarding ST, their opinion on whether screening for CST is within the SN scope, the importance of being informed about CSEC in their role, their level of confidence in identifying those at-risk, suspected CSEC cases, coercion and control methods, and red flags. Furthermore, questions were asked about participants' comfort level in questioning students about CSEC and their confidence in initiating interventions and following reporting procedures. Lastly, questions were posed concerning the availability of educational resources specific to SNs to raise CSEC awareness and whether they would take advantage of the opportunity to participate in CSEC preventive education.

SN Knowledge and Scope. When asked whether participants believed they understood ST adequately, most pre-survey participants (56.13%) reported they did not. On the contrary, more than 85% of post-survey respondents said they did. In their capacity as a SN, over 95% of pre- and post-survey participants reported that knowledge of CSEC is essential. Furthermore, slightly over 70% of pre-survey participants agreed that screening for CSEC falls under their purview; this percentage grew to 90% post-survey.

However, despite these positive findings, several gaps in SNs' attitudes and knowledge were highlighted. For example, most pre-survey participants reported a lack of confidence in identifying at-risk students and suspected cases, including red flags, high-risk situations, and the control and coercion methods used by exploiters (Appendix L, Table 2). Furthermore, $\geq 60\%$ of these participants also reported a lack of confidence and comfort in asking children questions about CSEC and initiating interventions. These findings are well documented in literature among SN participants, as well as HCPs and community members participants in multiple studies (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2018; Hartinger-Saunders et

al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022). Future research could examine the situational nature of educational needs, such as specialized regional training for healthcare workers and laypersons based on their respective communities' needs and geographical settings (Cole & Sprang, 2015; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013).

Interestingly, despite most pre-survey participants reporting a lack of confidence and comfort in the abovementioned factors, more than 70% reported they were aware of their mandatory reporting responsibilities in case of a suspected case. However, one participant noted a challenge regarding reporting, stating, “[I]n our county, schools are never sure CPS will actually follow up.” This was a shared feeling by HCP and SN participants in several studies, which led to feelings of untrustworthiness and uncertainty in the overall reporting process (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Hurst et al., 2021; Kraft et al., 2017).

Overall, a positive finding was that the post-survey data demonstrates that confidence, awareness, and attitudes increased in all previously mentioned factors- such as recognizing control and coercion methods and beginning interventions - and in some cases, the percentage doubled or tripled.

SN Education. Participants were asked if they had ever received HT education, about their perceptions of whether knowledge is a barrier to SNs identifying CSEC, and if they believed SNs have access to valuable educational resources to increase their CSEC-related knowledge. They were also asked if they would participate in preventative training if given the opportunity. The majority (57.77%) of pre-survey participants reported they had received HT education, which aligns with multiple studies (Donahue et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2020; Lutz, 2018; McMahon-Howard & Reimers, 2013; Rheingold et al., 2012). Conversely, 62% of post-survey participants reported that they had not.

Most respondents ($\geq 70\%$) believed that a lack of knowledge is a barrier, and over half of pre-survey respondents felt SNs lack access to CSEC-related educational materials; this dipped to 40% post-survey. A compelling finding was that an overwhelming majority ($\geq 94\%$) of pre- and post-survey participants affirmed their willingness to engage in educational opportunities specific to SNs to combat CSEC. Overall, these results are consistent with several studies on CA, including CST and CSA, where participants' time, educational materials, and need for continuing education were identified (Chappell et al., 2021; Fraley et al., 2018; Gardner et al., 2020).

CST Screening. Screening for CST in schools is critically important, considering that research findings indicate that victims of HT attend school (Fraley et al., 2018; Grace et al., 2012). Additionally, a significant number of survey respondents ($\geq 9\%$ pre- and 10% post-survey) reported encountering a victim. Screening will also help identify students who may be overlooked by SNs, as evidenced by the project's findings, where $\geq 20\%$ of participants were uncertain if they had encountered a victim.

As stated previously, most SN participants ($\geq 70\%$ pre- and $\geq 90\%$ post-survey) believed CST screening to be within their scope of practice. However, even with this belief, participants provided input on recommendations, concerns, and potential barriers to screening. Several participants expressed feeling uncomfortable due to the nature of the screening questions, parents' reactions to CST screening, and the worry about re-traumatization, all of which are noted in the literature (Chappell et al., 2021; Cole & Sprang, 2015; Kraft et al., 2017).

Furthermore, most post-survey participants believed that the recommended screening tool was more appropriate for middle and high school students, and developmentally appropriate questions for elementary-aged students were an identified need in several responses. In addition,

clear guidance on policies and protocols of what warrants tool usage and clear instructions for tool administration were recommended. Additionally, respondents included recommendations such as the need for a safe space for students to disclose and using therapeutic communication which was also noted across the literature (Chappell et al., 2021; Ellis et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2018a; Hartinger-Saunders et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2017; Murdock et al., 2022; Raible et al., 2017; Sekhar et al., 2018). One participant noted,

“I am sure the questionnaire comes with an instruction page BUT I hope that page includes instruction reminding the SN of privacy, hushed speaking tones, eye contact, and to acknowledge personal bias BEFORE speaking with student and to put the best possible game face on and NOT react to what the student is sharing, just listen and be supportive.”

Despite participants’ noting some concerns, an encouraging finding was that most post-survey respondents felt that the recommended CST screening tool was appropriate (Appendix O).

Societal

The societal level examines the societal and community awareness of CST, federal (i.e., TVPA) and state (i.e., AB 1227) HT laws and policies (Finigan-Carr et al., 2019). This level also includes HT position statements from professional organizations such as NASN and CSNO. Participants were asked about their awareness of ST nationally and whether they believed students could be victims and exploiters of this problem. Additionally, they were questioned on their familiarity with the term “CSEC” and if they perceived a connection between CST and CSA or poverty.

At this level, the key findings indicate that over 80% of the participants believed students could be victims. This is consistent with the findings of Fraley et al. (2018), who reported that 86.6% of their participants had the same belief. Yet, more than 80% of all participants in this project believed that students could also be exploiters, in contrast to the findings of the Fraley et al. (2018) study, where just 34.8% of participants held that belief.

Most participants were also aware of ST at the national level. Interestingly, although they had this awareness, less than half of the pre-survey participants were familiar with the term “CSEC.” Many participants demonstrated an understanding of the correlations between CST and CSA, as well as poverty. While this study is descriptive in nature and does not allow for making inferences, the percentage of participants who expressed awareness or agreement with the presented questions under this level increased from the pre- to the post-survey.

Another significant finding was the need for district protocols and policies specific to HT. In an open-text field response, multiple participants stated the need for explicit policies about and guidance on identification, screening, and what to do in the event of a disclosure on campus. Similarly, in a study by Raible et al. (2017), SN survey respondents expressed the necessity for district policies and protocols inclusive of guidance to address suspected adolescent relationship abuse. The authors argued that with these in place, administrator support and sustainability of the intervention were feasible (Raible et al., 2017).

The overall results of this project indicate that by analyzing the interactions between each level, the SEM is a valuable framework for understanding the complexity of CST and illuminating the pivotal role of SNs in this public health crisis.

Strengths and Limitations

One of the project's greatest strengths is that the participants work in various geographic and educational settings, including private and charter schools, with varying demographics, representing every section of CSNO, thus offering insightful data on the diversity of the State of California. In addition, respondents' educational backgrounds, years of SN experience, and HT education varied. Furthermore, four pre-survey participants self-identified as male, a surprising finding given that school nursing is predominantly female. Open-ended survey questions were an added strength since they gave the PI a more thorough understanding of respondents' viewpoints. Finally, the surveys were delivered anonymously and confidentially, and responses were de-identified to lessen the possibility of social desirability bias.

The challenge of recruiting participants for the post-survey, particularly, and the limited time window for survey administration were limitations of this project. Another drawback was the study's convenience sample, which consisted of primarily White female individuals, all of whom practice in California. The results' generalizability outside of the project's context may be limited by the convenience sample and absence of feedback from SNs who chose not to participate and might have had different opinions. However, despite these limitations, the project's findings support the small body of existing research and have significant practice implications for school nursing.

Implications for SN Practice

NASN and CSNO's HT position statements indicate that SNs, applying their astute clinical assessment skills, leadership, and public health knowledge, are well positioned to take an active role in CST identification, screening, education, and prevention (CSNO, 2022; NASN 2021). However, SNs must be aware of and knowledgeable about CST, have clear protocols and

policies highlighting their unique role, and have easy access to a tangible, evidence-based, validated CST screening tool. The findings of this project- the only CST-related study informed by CSNO members- have several implications for school nursing practice in California.

Education

Participants recommended- and the evidence supports- the need for sustained CST education for SNs. SNs need to be knowledgeable about CST and its presentation in the school setting. One way to address this is working with CDE and the California Commission on Teacher Credentialing to mandate that SN credentialing programs incorporate CST-related content in their curricula. Additionally, credentialed SNs can acquire the necessary knowledge of CST that may have diminished over time if there is ongoing collaboration between CSNO and California's Board of Registered Nursing to offer targeted continuing education on CST, including validated CST screening tools.

Practice and Policy

Exploiters of HT know where systems fail, including schools (Fraley et al., 2018; Grace et al., 2012; NASN, 2021) thus, CST policies and protocols must be in place across all of California's schools. Such policies should clearly outline red flags, reporting guidelines, and roles of school personnel, including the SN. It is advised that CSNO establish a SN working group that can collaborate with CDE and CDPH to create a statewide HT protocol template that schools can adapt to their needs. SN participants noted that administrators and school personnel's lack of support and inclusivity made it difficult for them to identify CSEC. Thus, a multidisciplinary approach must be needed to draft and implement these policies and protocols.

Research

Since it has never been implemented before, further research is needed to assess

Greenbaum et al.'s (2018b) tool in a school environment. As discussed, this tool was highly accepted among the study's post-survey participants and has been validated in other clinical and community settings with youth. Suggested recommendations include a small-scale rollout of the tool in one district situated in a community with known CST activity. Measures will include assessing whether the tool is used correctly, in what capacity it is used, the number of identified cases, and the number of confirmed cases.

Conclusions

These findings of this descriptive mixed methods study reinforce CST's individualistic, highly complex, and hidden nature and the need for sustained HT education geared to SNs so they can confidently educate, identify, screen, and prevent CST in their schools. When it comes to identifying students who are victims or at-risk, SNs will continue to miss opportunities due to a lack of awareness and the absence of a universal validated screening tool.

The SEM, which served as the project's conceptual framework, was the ideal multilevel framework since it provided a comprehensive perspective for understanding the intricate links between a student and external factors that may influence their victimization. Additionally, the SEM highlighted the important role SNs have in CST education, intervention, and prevention efforts. Driven by the SEM and informed by the literature and pre-survey data, the evidence-based educational module gave participants a comprehensive overview of HT, emphasizing the SN's role in anti-CST efforts. Additionally, participants were given the opportunity to offer input on a recommended validated CST screening tool. The open-field survey responses provided valuable insight into barriers they face in CST identification, tool revisions, and screening recommendations.

Comprehending the project outcomes through the SEM draws attention to the dynamic interchange among all levels. It also sheds light on our society's profound influence on local communities, including schools, regarding HT-related processes, policies, and resource distribution (i.e., education). Therefore, HT position statements issued by state and national SN professional organizations are inadequate on their own. Instead, HT policies and procedures tailored to the education sector and in line with CSNO and NASN position statements are needed. These include outlining the SN's role in CST prevention, education, and intervention efforts, requiring CST-related curricula in SN credential programs, and advocating for SNs at the federal, state, and local levels. This, in turn, will pave the way for SNs to assert their legitimate positions as respected renowned experts on school health, including the prevention of CST, at decision-making tables in all educational settings and protect students nationwide.

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Appendix A

The Socio-Ecological Model: A Framework for Prevention

Note. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022).

Appendix B

Adapted Socio-Ecological Model for CSEC/CST: A Lens for School Nurses

Appendix C

Literature Review Summary: Initial Search Strategy with Limiters

Topic	Search Terms	Search Term Combinations	EBSCO Host plus CINAHL	EBSCO Host plus ERIC	PubMed	Total
Human Trafficking	Child Sex Trafficking	Education	2	0	0	2
		Awareness OR knowledge OR understanding	3	0	0	3
		Prevention	4	0	0	0
		Screening Tool	6	0	1	7
		Healthcare provider or healthcare professional	0	0	2	2
		Nurse	0	0	0	0
		School Nurse	0	0	0	0
Child Sexual Abuse	Child Sexual Abuse	Screening Tool OR screening	9	22	0	31
		Prevention	11	16	5	32
		Education	3	22	12	37
		School Nurse	3	2	3	10

Appendix D

Literature Review Summary: Final Search Strategy with Limiters

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health (CINAHL)

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
School Nurse AND child abuse	Peer-reviewed, English language, 2000-2022, All Child, USA	14	12	2	0
School Nurse AND trafficking	Peer-reviewed, English language, 2000-2022, All Child, USA	6	2	4	3
Trafficking Screening Tool	Peer-reviewed, English language, 2000-2022, All Child, USA	3	1	2	1
Child sexual abuse AND screening	Peer-reviewed, English language, 2000-2022, All Child, USA	65	60	5	1

Note. Articles excluded were based on title, study type, population, and lack of project relevance.

Database: PubMed

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Child sex trafficking tool	English, 2000-2023, Child (birth-18 years), Clinical Trial, RCT, Observational Study, Comparative Study, Controlled Clinical Trial	4	3	1	0
Child sexual abuse tool	English, 2000-2023, Child (birth-18 years), Clinical Trial, RCT, Observational Study,	17	13	4	0

Comparative Study,
Controlled Clinical Trial

Child Trafficking	English, 2000-2023, Child (birth-18 years), Clinical Trial, RCT, Observational Study, Comparative Study, Controlled Clinical Trial	58	54	4	0
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Note. Articles excluded were based on title, study type, population, and lack of project relevance.

Database: OneSearch

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Child abuse education for school nurses	Peer Reviewed, articles, English, 2000-2023	471	429	42	4
Child trafficking education for nurses	Peer Reviewed, articles, English language, 2000-2023	52	33	19	1
Child abuse training for school nurses	Peer Reviewed, articles, English language, 2000-2023	149	131	18	2
School nursing screening tool for child abuse	Peer Reviewed, articles, English language, 2000-2023	118	107	11	1
School nursing screening tool for trafficking	Peer Reviewed, articles, English language, 2000-2023	44	35	9	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title, study type, population, and lack of project relevance.

Database: ERIC

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Child trafficking	2000-2023, Peer-reviewed, English	14	12	2	0

Sex trafficking AND minor	2000-2023, Peer- reviewed, English	8	6	2	0
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Note. Articles excluded were based on title, study type, population, and lack of project relevance.

Database: APA PsycInfo

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
School Nurse AND trafficking	2000-2022, Peer- reviewed, Journal Article, English	5	3	2	1
School Nurse AND abuse	2000-2022, Peer- reviewed, Journal Article, English	16	6	10	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title, study type, population, and lack of project relevance.

Appendix E

CSNO Letter of Support

CALIFORNIA SCHOOL NURSES ORGANIZATION

School Nurses Optimize Student Health and Enhance Learning

April 17, 2023

Emma Birur, MSN, RN, PHN
 Doctoral Candidate
 School of Nursing
 California State University, Fullerton

Dear Ms. Birur,

As the President of the California School Nurse Organization (CSNO), I am pleased to support your work to address the gap in knowledge and awareness of child trafficking, among school nurses by creating an evidence-based educational module and screening tool. We understand that California has one of the highest volumes of human trafficking in the United States (Human Rights Center, n.d.). In line with the National Association of School Nurses, we not only believe in the importance of human trafficking awareness among school nurses, but that the credentialed school nurse plays an integral part in the identification, education, and case management of students at risk for trafficking (CSNO, 2022; NASN, n.d.).

Research has demonstrated that trafficking victims attend school, therefore, school nurses are likely to encounter them (Fraleley et al., 2018; Grace et al., 2012). This creates an opportunity for school nurses to not only identify red flags but also intervene given that the trafficker is not physically present (Fraleley et al., 2018; Sekhar et al., 2018).

Developing an evidence-based child abuse educational module and screening tool, inclusive of trafficking, that is tailored to California school nurses for use in their practice setting is a noteworthy undertaking. A better understanding of the school nurse's role in trafficking identification, prevention and education can help to inform strategies and approaches to foster safer schools for our children.

3511 Del Paso Rd, Suite 160, PMB 230, Sacramento, CA 95835
 Phone - 916-448-5752 - FAX 844-273-0846
 Email csno@csno.org Website www.csno.org

CSNO is committed to helping you reach and recruit organization members for participation in your study to ensure an adequate sample and representation of needs across the state. We would be happy to assist you by distributing notice of this research opportunity to our members via email with two follow-up reminder emails after one week and one month.

We look forward to working with you during the 2023-2024 academic year on this very worthwhile and exciting project and wish you the best on this project.

Sincerely,

Dawn Anderson,
 California School Nurse Organization
 President 2023-2025

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Appendix F

School Nurse Awareness and Perceptions of Students At Risk Survey

Reference:

Fraley, H. & Aronowitz, T. (2021b). Psychometric evaluation of the school nurses' awareness and perceptions survey (SNAPS) for youth at-risk of trafficking. *Journal of Nursing Measurement*, 29(3), 462–475.

<https://doi.org/10.1891/JNM-D-20-00018>

School Nurse Awareness and Perceptions of Students At Risk Survey

Introduction to the Survey: This survey will help us understand knowledge level and opinions among school nurses regarding students at risk for Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children (CSEC). If you are a Registered Nurse and currently practicing or ever practiced in a school setting please read each question carefully and respond.

For this survey "at risk" includes the following definition of terms:

CSEC = Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children

Exploiters = Perpetrators who either sell or buy commercial sex

Sex trafficking = Holding a person or group of people against their will and forcing them to sell sex commercially

Section 1

Survey Instructions: Please read and respond to the questions by selecting the number that most appropriately represents your awareness

1 = not at all 2 = somewhat 3 = average 4 = above average 5 = very much

Considering the students you provide care for as a school nurse, how familiar are you with the following in your student population?

1. Academic achievement levels of students under your care?	1	2	3	4	5
2. Student absences and tardiness?	1	2	3	4	5
3. Social peer relationships of students?	1	2	3	4	5
4. Family relationships of students?	1	2	3	4	5
5. Social-emotional status of students?	1	2	3	4	5
6. Mental health diagnoses of students?	1	2	3	4	5
7. Dating relationships of students?	1	2	3	4	5
8. Students who are in foster care and/or Department of Children and Family (DCF) custody?	1	2	3	4	5
9. Students who are involved in the Juvenile Justice System?	1	2	3	4	5
10. Medical disability diagnoses of students?	1	2	3	4	5
11. Learning disability diagnoses of students?	1	2	3	4	5
12. The problem of human trafficking?	1	2	3	4	5
13. The term Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children (CSEC)?	1	2	3	4	5
14. The multiple forms of CSEC?	1	2	3	4	5
15. The scope of the CSEC problem—nationally and locally?	1	2	3	4	5
16. The term "throwaway" kids?	1	2	3	4	5
17. Control and coercion methods used by exploiters?	1	2	3	4	5

Section 2

Survey Instructions: Please read and respond to the questions by selecting the number that most appropriately represents your opinion

1 = not at all 2 = somewhat 3 = average 4 = above average 5 = very much

How strongly do you agree with the following?

18. Sex trafficking is a problem for students in the U.S.	1	2	3	4	5
19. Sex trafficking is a problem for students in my state	1	2	3	4	5
20. Child sexual abuse is related to child sex trafficking	1	2	3	4	5
21. CSEC victims always come from situations of poverty	1	2	3	4	5
22. Students who frequently runaway are emotionally at risk	1	2	3	4	5
23. Students who frequently runaway are difficult to work with	1	2	3	4	5
24. Runaways are more likely to identify as LGBTQ	1	2	3	4	5
25. Students can get out of trafficking by asking for help	1	2	3	4	5
26. Exploiters can be students at school	1	2	3	4	5

Section 3

Survey Instructions: Please read and respond to the questions by selecting the number that most appropriately represents your opinion

1 = not at all 2 = somewhat 3 = average 4 = above average 5 = very much

How strongly do you agree with the following?

27. CSEC is a major problem facing students today	1	2	3	4	5
28. It is important for me to know about CSEC for my role as a school nurse	1	2	3	4	5
29. It is appropriate for school nurses to screen students for CSEC	1	2	3	4	5
30. Knowledge of CSEC is a barrier for school nurses to identify CSEC	1	2	3	4	5
31. If educational opportunities were available to me to learn how to identify CSEC in my role as a school nurse I would attend	1	2	3	4	5

Appendix G

Awareness and Attitudes Assessment Pre-and Post-Survey

Adapted from Donahue et al., 2019, Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b, and Jordan et al., 2017.

Please circle your response to the following statements using a 5-point Likert Scale:

1-Strongly Disagree

2-Disagree

3-Uncertain

4-Agree

5-Strongly Agree

1. I am familiar with students' peer relationships.

1 2 3 4 5

2. I am familiar with students' familial relationships.

1 2 3 4 5

3. I am familiar with the social-emotional status of students.

1 2 3 4 5

4. I am familiar with the mental health diagnoses of students.

1 2 3 4 5

5. I am familiar with students in foster care and/or Department of Children and Family Services (DCFS) custody.

1 2 3 4 5

6. I believe that I have an adequate understanding of sex trafficking.

1 2 3 4 5

7. I am familiar with the problem of sex trafficking nationally.

1 2 3 4 5

8. Sex trafficking is not a problem in my community.

1 2 3 4 5

9. I am familiar with the term Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children (CSEC)?

1 2 3 4 5

10. I believe that students can be CSEC victims.

1 2 3 4 5

11. I believe that exploiters can be students.

1 2 3 4 5

12. I believe that there is a relationship between CSEC and child sexual abuse.

1 2 3 4 5

13. There is a relationship between CSEC and poverty.

1 2 3 4 5

14. I believe that it is within the school nurses' scope to screen for CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

15. I am confident in my ability to identify children at risk for CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

16. I am confident in my ability to identify suspected cases of CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

17. I am confident in my ability to recognize high-risk situations and red flags for CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

18. I am able to identify the control and coercion methods used by exploiters.

1 2 3 4 5

19. I am comfortable asking a child questions that pertain to CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

20. I am confident in my ability to begin interventions for a child suspected of being involved in CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

21. As a mandated reporter, I know what to do if I suspect a case of CSEC in the school setting.

1 2 3 4 5

22. I believe that knowledge is a barrier to identifying CSEC as a school nurse.

1 2 3 4 5

23. I believe that it is important to know about CSEC in my role as a school nurse.

1 2 3 4 5

24. I believe that school nurses have access to useful educational material to increase their awareness of CSEC.

1 2 3 4 5

25. If I were given the educational opportunity to learn my role as a School Nurse in the prevention of CSEC, I would take it.

1 2 3 4 5

26. Please list any barriers you see to identifying CSEC in your role as a school nurse.

27. Please write any comments or questions that you have about CSEC.

Additional Pre-Survey Only Questions:

28. Would you like to access the educational module and post-survey?

- a. No
- b. Yes

29. If yes, please provide your best email address to send the electronic educational module and post-survey.

Additional Post-Survey Only Questions:

1. Do you feel that Greenbaum's 6-item screening tool would be appropriate for school nurses to use in their setting?

1. No 2. Yes 3. Unknown

2. What additional input do you have regarding the tool? Are there any revisions or additions to the tool that would apply to school nursing care?

2. Since completing the educational module, do you have anything else to add?

Appendix H

Project Timeline

Completion Date	Activities
April 2023	Obtained a letter of support from CSNO
May 2023	Oral defense and final proposal
June-July 2023	Submitted a proposal for the 74th Annual CSNO Conference (2024) Tool development (obtained permission from authors)
August 2023	Drafted tentative outline for survey and educational module
September 2023	Applied to IRB and IRB approval letter (exempt) Conference proposal accepted Pre- and post-survey development Requested feedback on survey and email flier from team leader (TL), team member (TM), and CSNO president
October 2023	CSNO sent out pre-survey announcement email (October 4th & 18th) Educational module development
November 2023	CSNO sent out third reminder email (November 6th) Data collection (pre-survey including demographics) Final draft of educational module sent to TL, TM, CSNO president Pre-survey closed November 8th
December 2023	Data collection (cont.) Educational module and post-survey sent to interested pre-survey respondents who listed their emails (12/15) PI sent post-survey reminder email (12/19)
January 2024	CSNO sent out a reminder email re: post-survey to all CSNO listserv (1/8) PI emailed reminder to listed pre-survey participants only (1/17 & 1/22) PPT created for CSNO conference Post-survey closed January 29th
February 2024	Presented preliminary findings at two CSNO breakout sessions
March 2024	Post-survey data analysis, write up of results
April 2024	Submission of final DNP project Dissemination

Appendix I

IRB Approval Letter

Date: 9-8-2023

IRB #: HSR-22-23-410

Title: Unmasking Child Sex Trafficking: Education, Identification and Screening for California School Nurses

Creation Date: 5-11-2023

End Date:

Status: **Approved**

Principal Investigator: Emma Birur

Review Board: Exempt Board

Sponsor:

Study History

Submission Type	Initial	Review Type	Exempt	Decision	Exempt
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Key Study Contacts

Member	Hannah Fraley	Role	Co-Principal Investigator	Contact	hfraley@fullerton.edu
Member	Emma Birur	Role	Principal Investigator	Contact	ebirur@csu.fullerton.edu
Member	Emma Birur	Role	Primary Contact	Contact	ebirur@csu.fullerton.edu

Appendix J

Informed Consent Letter

Study Title: Unmasking Child Sex Trafficking: Education, Identification, and Prevention for California School Nurses.

Protocol Number: HSR-22-23-410

Researcher:

1. Emma Birur, DNP Candidate
School of Nursing, California State University, Fullerton
ebirur@csu.fullerton.edu

You are being asked to participate in a research study by Emma Birur under the advisement of Dr. Hannah Fraley. This consent form explains the research study and your part if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide not to participate in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of this research study is to create an evidence-based educational module to inform school nursing practice and develop a child abuse screening tool inclusive of trafficking tailored to California (CA) School Nurses (SN) for use in their school settings. The specific objectives are to a) assess the level of human trafficking awareness among CA SNs; b) develop and distribute an educational module addressing any knowledge gaps to all California School Nurses Organization (CSNO) members who responded to the initial survey; c) distribute a comprehensive, evidence-based child abuse screening tool inclusive of youth trafficking screening; and f) distribute post-surveys to assess the module's effect on CSEC/CST identification, intervention, and prevention.

You are being asked to participate in this study because you are a school nurse currently working in California and a CSNO member. You cannot participate in this study if you are not actively practicing as a school nurse in California, are not a member of CSNO, and are under 18. Study participation includes the completion of a pre-and post-survey and an educational module, which will take no more than 1 hour.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you participate in the research study, you will be asked to complete a pre- and post-survey and educational module. In the pre-survey, you will be asked demographic questions and questions regarding your overall understanding of human trafficking, including child sex trafficking's presentation, risk factors, encounters, and beliefs. The post-survey will exclude the demographic questions and ask participants to answer the same pre-survey questions regarding human trafficking. Both surveys will take no more than 15 minutes to complete. If you choose to complete the pre-survey you will be provided with a link to the educational module. You will have two months to complete the module and post-survey questions. You may refuse to answer any pre- and post-survey questions at any time. There will be no use of medical, academic, or

other records and no voice, video, digital, or image recordings. All survey results will be de-identified and reported in aggregate form.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

The potential benefits to you for participating in this study are: 1) increased awareness and knowledge about human trafficking and child sex trafficking including in the school setting; 2) input on what resources and educational you need as a school nurse in order to equip you in identifying at-risk youth; 3) first look at an adapted screening tool for use in the school setting; 4) access to an educational module tailored to school nurses in California; and 5) be a part of the first adapted child sex trafficking screening tool and educational module that is informed by CA school nurses.

If you take part in this study, you may help other school nurses in the future to identify current and at-risk students in the school setting.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

Although risks should be minimal, the potential risks from taking part in the study are psychological, including distress or discomfort, since survey questions and educational content are sensitive in nature. In order to minimize these risks, content warning signs will precede potentially sensitive content. At any point during the study, you may choose to refrain from answering specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. Under certain circumstances, information that identifies you may be released for internal and external reviews of this project. Participants' privacy will be maintained throughout the study by de-identifying survey results.

Data will be stored on a password-protected laptop with Apple FileVault software in a personal locked home office or kept on the researcher's person at all times. Data will be accessible to the principal investigator and her team leader.

The data for this study will be kept for a minimum of three years to inform future educational and professional development, presentations, and publications. The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain confidential.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no cost to you for taking part in this study. You will not receive money or any other compensation for participating in this study.

Whom can I contact if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please email the researcher Emma Birur at ebirur@csu.fullerton.edu.

If you have questions about your rights as a research participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. You will not be penalized if you choose not to participate. You may choose to refrain from answering specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my consent on this form mean?

Your consent on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
 - You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
 - The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
 - You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks involved.
-

Statement of Electronic Consent

I have carefully read and/or have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By clicking below and selecting “next” to proceed with the survey, I agree that I am at least 18 and agree to participate in this project. You may print this page for your records.

- AGREE
 DISAGREE

Appendix K

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Measure	Pre-Survey		Post-Survey	
	Frequency/Count	Percentage	Frequency/Count	Percentage
Gender				
Male	4	2.58%	0	0%
Female	150	96.77%	49	98%
Prefer not to state.	1	.65%	1	2%
Non-binary/third gender	0	0%	0	0%
Transgender	0	0%	0	0%
Age				
<30	8	5.16%	1	2%
31-40	29	18.71%	6	12%
41-50	46	29.68%	13	26%
51-60	48	30.97%	15	30%
>60	24	15.48%	14	28%
Prefer not to state.	0	0%	1	2%
Race				
American Indian or Alaska Native	1	.65%	0	0%
Asian	15	9.68%	5	10%
Black or African American	4	2.58%	2	4%
Native or Pacific Islander	3	1.94%	0	0%
White	110	70.97%	39	78%
Two or more races	7	4.52%	3	6%
Other/Unknown	7	4.52%	0	0%

Prefer not to state.	8	5.16%	1	2%
Ethnicity				
Hispanic or Latino	23	14.84%	4	8%
Not Hispanic or Latino	132	85.16%	46	92%
CSNO Section				
Bay Coast	23	14.84%	9	18%
Central Coast	16	10.32%	4	8%
Central Valley	28	18.06%	10	20%
Northern	34	21.94%	8	16%
San Diego-Imperial	10	6.45%	1	2%
Southern	44	28.39%	18	26%
Education Level				
Associates	1	.65%	0	0%
Bachelors	78	50.32%	19	38%
Masters	62	40%	23	46%
Doctorate	5	3.23%	3	6%
Other	9	5.81%	5	10%
SN Credential	6	66.66%	5	100%
Unspecified Certificate	1	11%	0	0%
Health Science Credential	1	11%	0	0%
Not Specified	1	11%	0	0%
Years of SN Experience				
1-5	57	36.77%	11	22%
6-10	36	23.23%	9	18%
11-15	23	14.84%	9	18%
16-20	9	5.81%	6	12%
21+	30	19.35%	15	30%
Geographical Setting*				

City	62	40%	11	22%
Rural	30	19.35%	6	12%
Suburban	52	33.55%	28	56%
Town	9	5.81%	5	10%
Other	2	1.29%	0	0%
Mixed	2	100%	0	0%
School Setting				
Charter	4	2.58%	1	2%
Private	6	3.87%	1	2%
Public	137	88.39%	45	90%
Other	8	5.16%	3	6%
County Office of Education	6	75%	3	100%
Not specified.	2	25%	0	0%
Grade Level				
Preschool	3	1.94%	1	2%
Elementary (K-6th)	12	7.74%	4	8%
Elementary (K-8th)	33	21.29%	12	24%
Middle	6	3.87%	1	2%
High	25	16.13%	5	10%
Adult School	0	0%	0	0%
Multiple Grade Levels	63	40.65%	23	46%
Other (please specify)	13	8.39%	4	8%
Preschool-6th	1	7.69%	0	0%
Preschool & K-8th	2	15.38%	0	0%
Elementary and Middle	0	0%	1	25%
PK-12	2	15.38%	0	0%
TK-22	1	7.69%	0	0%
Middle and High	1	7.69%	1	25%

K-12th	3	23.08%	0	0
Administration	1	7.69%	1	25%
All grades	1	7.69%	0	0%
Not specified.	1	7.69%	0	0%
Student Population				
Gen Ed	12	7.74%	2	4%
Special Ed	8	5.16%	2	4%
Both	135	87.10%	42	84%
Other (please specify)	0	0	4	8%
# School Assigned				
1	30	19.35%	5	10%
2	36	23.23%	9	18%
3	16	10.32%	12	24%
4+	49	31.61%	18	36%
Other (please specify)	24	15.48%	6	12%
Minority Enrollment**				
<25%	17	10.97%	3	6%
25-49%	44	28.39%	20	40%
50-74%	42	27.10%	15	30%
≥75%	52	33.55%	12	24%
Community Safety				
Crime is a problem	28	18.06%	7	24%
Crime is not a problem	33	21.29%	28	56%
Crime is somewhat of a problem	94	60.65%	15	30%
Previous HT Education				
No	59	38.06%	31	62%
Yes	88	56.77%	5	10%

I don't recall	8	5.16%	14	28%
HT Victim Encounter (School Setting)				
No	109	70.32%	31	62%
Yes	14	9.03%	5	10%
I'm not sure	32	20.65%	14	28%
Made a CPS Report in Past				
No	26	16.77%	5	10%
Yes	125	80.65%	45	90%
Prefer not to state	4	2.58%	0	0%
Called HT Hotline as a SN				
No	154	99.35%	50	100%
Yes	1	.65%	0	0%
Prefer not to state	0	0%	0	0%

Note. Table 1 depicts the percentage of pre- and post-survey participants for each descriptive measure.

* National Center for Education Statistics local definitions

**CA Dept of Ed's minority definition: " a student who is American Indian/Alaska Native, Asian, African American, Filipino, Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander, Hispanic, or Two or More Races Not Hispanic."

Appendix L

Table 2: Pre- and Post-Survey: Awareness and Attitudes Assessment Results

Table 2

Pre- and Post-Survey: Awareness and Attitudes Assessment Results

Statement	Pre-Survey (n=155)				Post-Survey (n=50)			
	Unaware/Disagree		Aware/Agree		Unaware/Disagree		Aware/Agree	
	Frequency/ Count	Percentage	Frequency/ Count	Percentage	Frequency/ Count	Percentage	Frequency/ Count	Percentage
I am familiar with students' peer relationships.	64	41.29%	91	58.71%	26	52%	24	48%
I am familiar with students' familial relationships.	66	42.58%	89	57.42%	19	38%	31	62%
I am familiar with the social-emotional status of students.	39	25.16%	116	74.84%	12	24%	38	76%
I am familiar with the mental health diagnoses of students.	33	21.29%	122	78.71%	7	14%	43	86%
I am familiar with students in foster care and/or Department of Children and Family Services (DCFS) custody.	52	33.55%	103	66.45%	12	24%	38	76%
I believe that I have an adequate understanding of sex trafficking.	87	56.13%	68	43.87%	6	12%	44	88%
I am familiar with the problem of sex trafficking nationally.	47	30.32%	108	69.68%	7	14%	43	86%

Sex trafficking is not a problem in my community.	150	96.77%	5	3.23%	49	98%	1	2%
I am familiar with the term Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children (CSEC).	89	57.42%	66	42.58%	11	22%	39	78%
I believe that students can be CSEC victims.	16	10.32%	139	89.68%	2	4%	48	96%
I believe that exploiters can be students.	27	17.42%	128	82.58%	3	6%	47	94%
I believe that there is a relationship between CSEC and child sexual abuse.	12	7.74%	143	92.26%	1	2%	49	98%
There is a relationship between CSEC and poverty.	26	16.77%	129	83.23%	3	6%	47	94%
I believe that it is within the school nurses' scope to screen for CSEC.	43	27.74%	112	72.26%	5	10%	45	90%
I am confident in my ability to identify children at risk for CSEC.	123	79.35%	32	20.65%	24	48%	26	52%
I am confident in my ability to identify suspected cases of CSEC.	124	80%	31	20%	23	46%	27	54%
I am confident in my ability to recognize high-risk situations and red flags for CSEC.	99	63.87%	56	36.13%	14	28%	36	72%
I am able to identify the control and coercion methods used by exploiters.	111	71.61%	44	28.39%	15	30%	35	70%
I am comfortable asking a child questions that pertain to CSEC.	94	60.65%	61	39.35%	18	36%	32	64%

I am confident in my ability to begin interventions for a child suspected of being involved in CSEC.	112	72.26%	43	27.74%	17	34%	33	66%
As a mandated reporter, I know what to do if I suspect a case of CSEC in the school setting.	42	27.10%	113	72.90%	3	6%	47	94%
I believe that knowledge is a barrier to identifying CSEC as a school nurse.	34	21.94%	121	78.06%	9	18%	41	82%
I believe that it is important to know about CSEC in my role as a school nurse.	4	2.58%	151	97.42%	2	4%	48	96%
I believe that school nurses have access to useful educational material to increase their awareness of CSEC.	89	57.42%	66	42.58%	20	40%	30	60%
If I were given the educational opportunity to learn my role as a School Nurse in the prevention of CSEC, I would take it.	8	5.16%	147	94.84%	3	6%	47	94%

Appendix M

Greenbaum et al.'s (2018b) CST Screening Tool

Reference:

Greenbaum, V.J., Livings, M. S., Lai, B. S., Edinburgh, L., Baikie, P., Grant, S. R., Kondis, J., Petska, H. W., Bowman, M. J., Legnano, L., Kas-Osoka, O., & Self-Brown, S. (2018b). Evaluation of a tool to identify child sex trafficking victims in multiple healthcare settings. *Journal of Adolescent Health, 63*(6), 745–752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohea.2018.06.032>

Short Screen for Child Sex Trafficking (CST) for the Healthcare Setting

Suggested introduction: “Hello. We often ask teens some questions to find out a little more about what is going on in their lives. It helps us understand more about how we might be able to offer help. Some of the questions are sensitive and may make you feel uncomfortable so it is important to know that *you do not have to answer the questions if you don't want to*. If you decide to answer them, it will help us with your evaluation. Answers to some of the questions may be included in your general medical record. I am generally able to keep what you tell me private (or confidential). There are two exceptions to this. The first is if you tell me there is a threat to your safety or the safety of someone else. The second is if we are required by law to share information in our medical record. Do you understand these exceptions? If not, please ask us and we are happy to explain.”

Give child the questionnaire, or ask the questions outside the presence of the person(s) accompanying the child if at all possible.

Screening Questions:

- 1) Have you ever broken any bones, had any cuts that required stitches, or been knocked unconscious? **
 No Yes
- 2) Some kids have a hard time living at home and feel that they need to run away. Have you ever run away from home? No Yes
- 3) Kids often use drugs or drink alcohol, and different kids use different drugs. Have you used drugs or alcohol in the last 12 months? No. Yes
- 4) Sometimes kids have been involved with the police. Maybe for running away, for breaking curfew, for shoplifting. There can be lots of different reasons. Have you ever had any problems with the police?
 No Yes
- 5) If you have had sex before, how many sexual partners have you had?
 0 partners 1-5 partners 6-10 partners >10 partners
- 6) Have you ever had a sexually transmitted disease (STD), like herpes or gonorrhea or chlamydia or trichomonas?
 No Yes

Scoring the Questionnaire

Question 5 is considered ‘positive’ if child reports >5 sexual partners.

Positive answers to 2 or more questions is considered a ‘positive screen’ (e.g. high risk). *However, further information will be needed to determine whether or not a child is actually being trafficked.* Additional information may be obtained by the provider or by a designated staff member with trauma training. Keep in mind that the ultimate goal of the healthcare provider is not to obtain a disclosure of trafficking, but to determine level of risk and patient needs so that appropriate resources can be offered, based on the information available to you. A trauma-informed approach and careful monitoring of the patient (including body language) is necessary so that signs of discomfort can be identified and addressed promptly if they should occur. Below is a sample of questions to consider in assessing level of risk, although other questions may be used. For example, asking if the patient would feel comfortable telling you about the experience leading to a positive survey response may open the door to further discussion of risk factors, or to

reassurance that the risk is relatively low. (Ex. If child endorsed running away from home, the provider could ask, “Do you feel comfortable telling me a bit about the last time you ran?”) Additional information about risk may be available from other sources (patient record, other staff). It is important to use the information obtained from your questions to determine potential resources and referrals that may benefit the patient, improve safety and lower risk of exploitation (for example, homeless shelters, LGBTQ resources, food pantries, mental health services). Depending on your level of concern for trafficking, and whether or not you are a mandated reporter, you may need to contact authorities in addition to offering resources. Mandatory reporting laws do NOT require the provider to be certain the child is being trafficked, but typically require a ‘reasonable’ degree of suspicion. This is why assessment of risk level is important whereas a disclosure of trafficking is not necessary. Know your mandatory reporting laws. Again, all interactions with the patient should be trauma-informed, victim-centered and culturally sensitive.

Sample follow-up questions to help assess level of risk:

Follow up on any screening question that was answered in the affirmative. When possible, use open-ended questions such as, “Do you feel comfortable telling me about it?”

Has a boyfriend, a girlfriend or anyone else ever asked you to do something sexual with *another* person (including oral sex, vaginal sex or anal sex with someone else)?

No Yes

Do you feel comfortable telling me about it? _____

Has anyone ever asked you to do some sexual act in public, like dance at a bar or a strip club?

No Yes

Do you feel comfortable telling me about it? _____

Sometimes kids are in a position where they really need food, clothing, a place to stay, or they want to buy something for themselves or someone else. But they don’t have money so they have to exchange sex for what they need. Have you ever been faced with a situation like that?

No Yes

Do you feel comfortable telling me about it? _____

Has anyone ever asked you to pose in a sexy way for a photo or a video?

No Yes

Do you feel comfortable telling me about it? _____

Note:

** Data from a recent study suggested that altering Question 1 improved specificity by nearly 10%, while sensitivity remained stable. The altered form of the question is:

“Have you ever been knocked unconscious?” (that is, eliminate mention of fractures and cuts)

1. Greenbaum VJ, Livings MS, Lai BS, Edinburgh L, Baikie P, Grant SR, Kondis J, Petska HW, Bowman MJ, Legano L, Kas-Osoka O, Self-Brown S. Evaluation of a tool to identify child sex trafficking victims in multiple healthcare settings J Adolescent Health, 2018 (in press).

Appendix N**Post-Survey Feedback of Greenbaum et al.'s (2018b) Screening Tool**

Measure	Frequency/Count	Percentage
Appropriability in School Setting		
No	1	2%
Yes	46	92%
Unknown	3	6%

Appendix O

Word Cloud: School Nurse Barriers

